

D2.4 Action Plans for R&I Strategy Implementation

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Deliverable Author(s):	Sasa Petkovic, Stojan Debarliev, Elona Pojani

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DISCLAIMER

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ACRONYMS

ACRONYM	FULL NAME
AI	Artificial Intelligence
EI CENTRE	Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation
ERA	European Research Area
EU	European Union
EUREKA	Intergovernmental organisation for research and development funding and coordination
COST	European Cooperation in Science and Technology
FEUN	Faculty of Economics University of Niš
FEUT	Faculty of Economics, University of Tirana
FEUSK	Faculty of Economics, St. Cyril & Methodius University in Skopje
FEUBL	Faculty of Economics, University of Banja Luka
K&TT	Knowledge and Technology Transfer
KETs	Key Enabling Technologies
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
MSMEs	Micro, Small and Medium-sized enterprises
MSTDI	Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
R&D	Research and Development
R&I	Research and Innovation
RAS	Development Agency of Serbia
S3	Smart Specialisation Strategy
S4	Smart Specialisation Strategy of the Republic of Serbia
SMEs	Small and medium-sized enterprises
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics
TRL	Technology Readiness Levels
TTOs	Technology Transfer Offices
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization

ACTION PLANS FOR R&I STRATEGY IMPLEMENTATION, FEUN, SERBIA

1. Executive Summary

Widening countries, including Serbia, face multiple challenges in developing robust entrepreneurial and innovation ecosystems such as limited access to finance, underdeveloped infrastructure, weak academia-industry collaboration, and low research and development (R&D) investment. However, these regions also hold significant untapped potential: a growing pool of educated youth, expanding digital connectivity, emerging innovation hubs, and access to EU funding. Targeted investments in human capital, knowledge institutions, and cross-sector partnerships are key to unlocking this potential.

Research and Innovation (R&I) are fundamental drivers of transformation and competitiveness. For widening countries, strengthening R&I capacity is essential not only to catch up with more advanced economies, but also to build resilience and autonomy in key sectors. R&I fosters startup creation, academic-industry collaboration, talent retention, and the development of smart, sustainable, and inclusive solutions, shifting regions from being consumers to producers of innovation.

This Strategy is fully aligned with national and European frameworks, especially **Serbia's Smart Specialisation Strategy (S4)**, focusing on **ICT, Food for the Future, and Creative Industries**. It also aligns with the **Horizon Europe** programme, the **European Green Deal**, the **Green Agenda for the Western Balkans**, and the **EU Digital Strategy**. This alignment ensures strategic coherence and increases access to international funding, partnerships, and impact.

Universities and faculties play a central role in implementing the Strategy as part of the knowledge triangle of education, research, and innovation. Their contributions include generating knowledge, training future innovators, supporting technology transfer, and building collaborative networks. The Faculty of Economics, University of Niš, is particularly well-positioned to bridge academic knowledge with practical entrepreneurship and innovation tools.

At the core of the Strategy's implementation is the **Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation (EI Centre)** which serves as an operational and strategic hub. It provides:

- Start-up and scale-up support,
- Capacity-building in innovation, entrepreneurship, and digital skills,
- Collaboration facilitation between academia, industry, and international partners,
- Infrastructure for technology transfer and prototyping,
- Support for inclusivity, particularly youth and women entrepreneurship.

The EI Centre supports long-term institutional commitment and impact tracking, helping to turn research outputs into real-world solutions that drive economic growth and create societal value.

2. Key Pillars of the R&I Strategy

2.1. Research Excellence

Promoting research excellence requires continuous investment in infrastructure, services, and collaborative environments. A strong research culture based on mentorship, diversity, openness, and international collaboration is essential for nurturing talent and producing impactful research. Inspired by leading models of academic excellence, the strategy aims to support researchers across all career stages by fostering interdisciplinary work, enhancing PhD and postdoctoral programs, and increasing externally funded projects.

Efforts will focus on building world-class facilities, attracting international partners, and boosting industry collaboration through joint research initiatives and doctoral training centres. Embedding a culture where innovation and public engagement are core to research practices will ensure that scientific output is translated into real-world social and economic impact.

2.2. Technology Transfer and Exploitation

Converting research into tangible societal and market value depends on efficient knowledge and technology transfer (K&TT). This process enables the flow of ideas, inventions, and intellectual property from research institutions to businesses, public institutions, and end-users. Key actors including universities, government, and industry must be supported by intermediary structures like Technology Transfer Offices to bridge the gap between innovation and application.

Core activities include IP protection, business model development, licensing, and use of tools such as Technology Readiness Levels (TRL). A modern approach to technology transfer also prioritizes sustainability by encouraging integrated solutions that simultaneously address environmental, economic, and societal goals. These efforts help drive economic growth, especially in emerging sectors.

2.3. Innovative Entrepreneurship

Innovative entrepreneurship is a key engine for long-term economic growth, especially in less developed economies. Unlike traditional entrepreneurship focused mainly on job creation, innovative entrepreneurship generates high-value jobs, competitive firms, and novel solutions to societal challenges.

It combines the development of new products, services, or business models with the agility of start-ups. However, many early-stage firms lack the R&D capacity to be recognized by conventional innovation metrics like patents or R&D spending. That is why broader indicators, such as combined product and process innovation, are recommended.

Creating an enabling environment for innovative entrepreneurship involves both macro- and micro-level interventions. At the macro level, secure property rights, legal certainty, and access to capital are critical. At the micro level, targeted support such as accelerators, incubators, and training programs helps firms with proven market potential to grow. Instead of trying to “pick winners,” public policy should focus on “retaining winners” by identifying and supporting high-potential firms that demonstrate real innovation capacity.

3. Strategic Enablers and Key Initiatives

The successful implementation of a comprehensive R&I Strategy requires not only visionary goals but also the foundational conditions that make those goals achievable. These foundations, or **strategic enablers**, represent the critical elements that ensure institutional coordination, policy alignment, and capacity building across the national innovation ecosystem. At the same time, **key initiatives** translate strategic vision into tangible actions, enabling systemic transformation and real-world impact.

This chapter outlines the core enablers and initiatives necessary for realizing the objectives of the R&I Strategy. The first three components: **governance, national strategy, and the role of universities**, serve as structural enablers, providing the institutional, policy, and academic foundation for sustained innovation. The following five areas, namely **cultural change, international orientation,**

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stakeholder communication, digital transformation, and green transition, represent strategic initiatives that catalyse change, drive inclusion, and align the innovation system with global priorities.

The development of these enablers, together with the implementation of forward-looking initiatives, will allow Serbia to build a resilient, competitive, and collaborative research and innovation ecosystem that is internationally connected, socially responsive, and capable of addressing complex societal and economic challenges.

3.1. Governance

Effective governance is essential for implementing a comprehensive R&I Strategy. In Serbia, the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation serves as the central institution responsible for developing science and technology policy, supporting research programs, promoting innovation, strengthening technology transfer, and enabling participation in European initiatives. Quality assurance of research activities is ensured through several national bodies, including the National Council for Scientific and Technological Development, the Committee for Accreditation of Research Organizations, and specialized scientific committees.

The Innovation Fund and the Science Fund form the backbone of the national science and innovation system. The Innovation Fund supports links between science and industry and encourages the development of innovative entrepreneurship, while the Science Fund finances high-quality, competitive, and socially relevant research through thematic programs. The Development Agency of Serbia complements these efforts by promoting investment, export growth, and the competitiveness of enterprises. Together with science and technology parks, incubators, and clusters, these institutions create a supportive environment aligned with EU standards and international funding mechanisms.

3.2. National R&I Strategy

Serbia has developed a comprehensive strategic framework that guides the development of research and innovation. The Strategy for Scientific and Technological Development 2021–2025 (“The Power of Knowledge”) strengthens research institutions, infrastructure, and international integration, and a new 2025–2029 strategy is currently under preparation. The Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) for 2020–2027 identifies priority areas for innovation-driven economic development, including ICT, food industry, creative industries, advanced manufacturing, key enabling technologies, and sustainable energy. These strategic documents provide continuity, define national priorities, and support the transformation of the economic structure through innovation.

3.3. Universities

Universities are key drivers of innovation and central stakeholders in the R&I system. As generators of new knowledge, they conduct research, develop talent, and support innovation through interdisciplinary curricula and participation in national and international programs. Their role in connecting with industry—through technology transfer, collaboration projects, science and technology parks, and business incubators—facilitates the commercialization of research and strengthens the competitiveness of the economy.

Universities also contribute to strategic planning and policymaking by providing expertise, participating in the design and evaluation of national strategies, and supporting evidence-based

reforms. Their proactive engagement is essential for building an integrated innovation ecosystem where knowledge, institutions, industry, and society operate in synergy.

3.4. Cultural change

A successful R&I Strategy requires embedding innovation culture across society, universities, and the business sector. Student involvement in entrepreneurial and creative initiatives—such as competitions, hackathons, and innovation events—strengthens the startup ecosystem and fosters a proactive mindset. At universities, knowledge transfer must become a core mission supported by incentive systems that encourage researchers and students to engage in entrepreneurial ventures. Businesses must recognize innovation as a strategic priority and deepen cooperation with academia, while the public sector should adopt innovative solutions and remove barriers to collaboration. Building public awareness of the importance of innovation through targeted communication and celebrating local success stories is crucial for developing a long-term entrepreneurial culture and a resilient national innovation ecosystem.

3.5. International orientation

Strengthening Serbia's international integration is essential for improving research quality and ensuring long-term sustainability of the R&I system. International cooperation enhances access to knowledge, increases research capacity, and strengthens global competitiveness.

At the Faculty of Economics, internationalisation is a key development direction. Cooperation with universities and institutions abroad improves teaching and research quality, supports mobility programs, and creates opportunities for joint projects under Erasmus+, Horizon Europe, and other EU initiatives. The EI Centre plays a central role as a connector between academia, industry, and international partners, supporting innovation initiatives and student development.

Increasing the number of foreign students and lecturers, developing study programs in English, and fostering global competencies further strengthen the Faculty's international position. Establishing institutional mechanisms for international collaboration and project management ensures long-term engagement in European research and innovation networks.

3.6. Stakeholders' communication

As Serbia prepares new strategic directions within the Smart Specialisation framework, continuous dialogue with stakeholders is essential for adapting the innovation system to emerging global and local trends. Clear and effective communication of the goals, reforms, and achievements of the R&I Strategy is crucial for building trust and increasing stakeholder engagement.

A comprehensive branding and communication strategy will help highlight the societal and economic impact of research and innovation. The Faculty of Economics and the EI Centre will contribute through outreach activities, media visibility, public events, and collaboration with business and international partners. Targeted international communication campaigns will support the Faculty's positioning as a regional leader in economics, innovation, and entrepreneurship.

3.7. Digital transformation

Digital transformation is a key enabler of innovation and a driver of economic modernization. Serbia's rapidly growing ICT sector plays a dual role: contributing to national economic development and leading digital transformation across industries and institutions. Digitalization requires the alignment of infrastructure, skills, technologies, and policy frameworks.

National initiatives—including the Digital Economy Strategy 2022–2027, the Artificial Intelligence Strategy 2022–2027, and Serbia's integration with EU digital networks—support these efforts. Digital public services (e-government) further enhance transparency, reduce bureaucracy, and improve efficiency.

Within academia, the Faculty of Economics and the EI Centre build digital competencies, support digital entrepreneurship, participate in international projects, and contribute to the development of innovative solutions. These efforts prepare students and researchers for global digital competitiveness.

3.8. Green transformation

The green transformation aims to reduce environmental impact and promote sustainable growth through renewable energy, circular economy models, green technologies, and resource efficiency. Although environmental research in Serbia has a long tradition, the green technology sector remains underdeveloped, creating new opportunities for growth and innovation.

National initiatives—such as the Energy Efficiency and Renewable Energy Plan, the Circular Economy Strategy, and green development programs—are essential in guiding the transition. Serbia also benefits from participation in EU climate initiatives, cross-border cooperation programs, and funding instruments supporting ecological innovation.

The Faculty of Economics and the EI Centre contribute by integrating sustainability into education, supporting green entrepreneurship, collaborating with government and industry on relevant projects, and organizing events focused on environmentally responsible business practices. Through these efforts, they help position green transformation as a strategic pillar of Serbia's innovation-driven development.

4. Roles and Responsibilities

The effective implementation of the R&I Strategy requires a clear definition of the roles and responsibilities of all key actors within the innovation ecosystem. In an environment shaped by a complex network of institutions, organizations, and individuals, coordinated collaboration is essential for achieving strategic goals. Clearly defined responsibilities ensure transparency, prevent overlap, and allow for resources to be allocated where they are most needed. Moreover, understanding the complementary roles of different actors helps build trust and strengthen partnerships both within and beyond national borders. Each group has distinct roles and responsibilities within the action plan, ensuring both coordination and accountability.

Government and public institutions form the foundation of the national innovation system. The **Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation (MSTDI)** plays a central role in designing and implementing national science and innovation policies. It defines strategic priorities, allocates public funds for R&I activities, and monitors the implementation of national programs. The Ministry also coordinates key national initiatives, such as strategies for artificial intelligence, technology transfer, and programs supporting young researchers.

Complementing the Ministry's work, the **Innovation Fund** and the **Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia** provide crucial financial support for research and innovation through competitive calls for proposals. These funds are essential for encouraging collaboration between science and industry, fostering the commercialization of research outputs, and enhancing Serbia's participation in global innovation networks. Additionally, the **Development Agency of Serbia (RAS)** promotes entrepreneurship, facilitates investment and export growth, and strengthens the competitiveness of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). RAS plays a significant role in building innovation capacity, particularly within the private sector.

Universities and research institutions also serve as key enablers of the innovation ecosystem. Institutions such as the **University of Niš** function as centres for generating new knowledge through academic research and innovation. They are active participants in international programs like Horizon Europe and Erasmus+, and they play a major role in nurturing human capital and developing entrepreneurial skills. By aligning educational and research activities with the needs of the economy, universities help bridge the gap between academia and industry. Faculties and research centres implement scientific and innovation projects, often in collaboration with industrial partners. Through partnerships with science and technology parks, innovation centres, and start-up incubators, they facilitate the transfer of research results into market-ready applications.

Entrepreneurs and startups are the driving force of innovation. Start-ups, spin-offs, and spin-out companies are often founded on new research ideas and technologies. They act as engines of innovation, commercializing research outputs and collaborating with universities through mentorship programs, accelerators, and funding mechanisms. **SMEs**, on the other hand, are crucial for implementing innovation in practice. They frequently engage in joint projects with research institutions and represent a key target group for national strategies on digitalization and green transformation.

Investors and financial institutions play a pivotal role in funding the innovation journey. **Investment funds** and **venture capital firms** provide early-stage financing to start-ups and scaleups, supporting their growth and long-term development. These investors often bring not only capital but also strategic guidance, helping shape high-potential ventures. **Public and development banks**, meanwhile, contribute to innovation financing by offering grants, subsidized loans, and guarantee schemes that lower the risk for innovative projects and encourage private-sector engagement.

Innovation infrastructure and intermediary organizations are vital in connecting actors within the ecosystem. **Science and technology parks** and **business incubators** offer critical infrastructure, mentorship, and access to networks that support start-ups and SMEs in their development. These institutions help translate academic knowledge into market-driven solutions and create an environment conducive to innovation. **Technology transfer offices (TTOs)** and innovation units within universities facilitate the protection of intellectual property, commercialization of research, and development of sustainable business models.

Finally, **policymakers and international partners** shape the regulatory and strategic environment for R&I. At both national and local levels, policymakers are responsible for developing and implementing supportive policies for science, innovation, and entrepreneurship. They ensure alignment with European Union standards and strategic frameworks such as the Smart Specialisation Strategy and the Green Agenda. **International organizations and funding programs**, including the EU, UN, and EIB, provide essential technical assistance and financial support, while also enabling Serbian stakeholders to access and participate in global research and innovation networks.

Through clearly defined roles and effective collaboration, these stakeholders form a cohesive system capable of driving the transformation toward a knowledge-based, innovation-driven economy in Serbia. The successful implementation of the Strategy depends on coordinated action among all relevant actors, from government institutions and the academic community to the private sector and

civil society. Clearly mapped roles allow for better resource management, faster execution of strategic activities, and higher overall system efficiency. With cross-sectoral collaboration and strategic alignment with international partners, Serbia can make significant progress toward a knowledge- and innovation-driven economy.

5. Timeline and Milestones

A clear and realistic timeline is essential for the effective implementation of the R&I Strategy. It enables structured execution of planned activities, helps allocate resources efficiently, and provides a basis for regular monitoring and evaluation.

The implementation of the R&I Action Plan at the Faculty of Economics will be carried out through a clearly defined timeline structured in **five key phases**, covering the period from **Q1 2026 to Q4 2028**. Each phase will include specific initiatives coordinated by the EI Centre, in collaboration with academic staff, students, business partners, and international institutions.

This approach emphasizes practical steps, institutional integration, and sustained progress, with a strong focus on capacity development, collaboration with the private sector, and knowledge transfer through structured training and mentoring. Phases of implementation include (Table 1):

1. **Capacity Building** (Q1–Q2 2026)
2. **Institutionalization** (Q3–Q4 2026)
3. **Initial Implementation** (Q4 2026 – Q2 2027)
4. **Scale-up and Consolidation** (Q3 2027 – Q2 2028)
5. **Evaluation and Strategy Revision** (Q3 – Q4 2028)

Table 1: Timeline of Activities

◆ <i>Phase 1: Capacity Building (Q1–Q2 2026)</i>
• Design and launch internal training programs through the EI Centre, targeting students, researchers, and teaching staff
• Establish a structured mentorship program with experts from industry and academia
• Conduct workshops on entrepreneurship, innovation management, and digital skills
• Develop and test the EI Centre’s online platform designed to support collaboration, knowledge exchange, and project development
• Map external partners for potential collaboration (companies, investors, innovation hubs)
◆ <i>Phase 2: Institutionalization (Q3–Q4 2026)</i>
• Integrate entrepreneurship and innovation activities into faculty frameworks and policies
• Formalize collaboration frameworks with private companies (MoUs, internship agreements, joint projects)
• Launch the full version of the EI Centre’s digital platform with resources, project calls, and networking functions
• Initiate joint industry-academia workshops and networking events
• Start piloting mentorship cycles and internal innovation challenges for students and researchers
◆ <i>Phase 3: Initial Implementation (Q4 2026 – Q2 2027)</i>
• Roll out student startup support programs (bootcamps, pre-incubation, early-stage funding opportunities)

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Begin implementation of multidisciplinary project teams involving students, mentors, and business partners
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organize first demo day for student and research-based ventures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expand training modules based on demand (e.g., green entrepreneurship, digital business models)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Launch applied research mini-projects in cooperation with selected companies
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Initiate mobility and cooperation programs with international academic and business partners
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ <i>Phase 4: Scale-up and Consolidation (Q3 2027 – Q2 2028)</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scale up entrepreneurship training to additional departments and student groups
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthen the alumni innovation network and involve former students as mentors and investors
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase visibility of the EI Centre through targeted communication and participation in international events
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expand the mentorship program to include international experts and diaspora professionals
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop and publish case studies of successful innovation projects and collaborations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create a structured system for monitoring and evaluating startup teams and applied research outputs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ <i>Phase 5: Evaluation and Strategy Revision (Q3 – Q4 2028)</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct a comprehensive review of the Action Plan implementation with input from all stakeholders
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organize an internal strategy workshop to identify strengths, weaknesses, and new opportunities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Update the EI Centre’s strategic priorities and work plan for 2029–2033
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publish a report with key findings, recommendations, and success stories
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Present results to institutional leadership and external partners to ensure long-term support

For effective monitoring, key milestones have been established to track progress and guide implementation. They denote important stages in the process, reflecting the completion of core activities or movement between project phases (Table 2).

Table 2: Key Implementation Milestones

Milestone	Target period
EI Centre’s internal training program launched	Q2 2026
Mentorship program piloted	Q3 2026
EI Centre I’s digital platform launched	Q4 2026
First industry-academia project team formed	Q1 2027
First demo day organized	Q2 2027
Cross-department innovation training scaled	Q1 2028
Internal strategy review completed	Q3 2028
Updated innovation action plan adopted	Q4 2028

These milestones serve as checkpoints to assess progress, address potential delays, and ensure alignment with broader strategic goals. Progress will be tracked semi-annually and reported to the

relevant ministries and stakeholder bodies. The visual project timeline provided (e.g., in the form of a Gantt chart) clearly illustrates the duration, sequencing, and interdependencies of all planned activities.

The EI Centre will serve as the central coordination unit for all innovation-related activities. Monitoring tools will be developed as part of the Centre’s digital platform to track progress on training, project development, mentorship engagement, and industry partnerships. Regular progress reports and consultations with stakeholders will ensure alignment with the broader goals of research excellence, entrepreneurship promotion, and local economic impact. This timeline not only ensures timely and structured execution, but also enables adaptive learning, allowing the Faculty of Economics and its EI Centre to respond to emerging needs and opportunities in the innovation ecosystem (Table 3).

Table 3: Key initiatives as Implementation Facilitators

Phase	Description	Key Initiative Focus
Capacity Building (Q1–Q2 2026)	Focus on developing institutional capacity, training, mentorship programs, and foundational frameworks.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stakeholder Communication: Begin creating communication channels and engagement tools. - Innovation Culture: Initiate awareness and education campaigns within the Centre. - International Orientation: Start building partnerships with international networks and programs. - Digital Transformation: Conduct capacity assessment and knowledge workshops. - Green Transformation: Begin regulatory review and sustainability awareness training.
Institutionalization (Q3–Q4 2026)	Formal establishment of programs and operational frameworks within the Centre and partner organizations.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stakeholder Communication: Formalize platforms for regular dialogue between all stakeholders. - Innovation Culture: Launch initiatives to embed innovation values and practices. - International Orientation: Develop joint programs with international partners. - Digital Transformation: Establish pilot projects and infrastructure for digital initiatives. - Green Transformation: Develop policies and guidelines for green innovation pilots.

<p>Initial Implementation (Q4 2026 – Q2 2027)</p>	<p>Rollout of pilot initiatives and programs with early adopters and selected start-ups/enterprises.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Digital Transformation: Launch pilot digital innovation projects. - Green Transformation: Start pilot projects testing green solutions. - Stakeholder Communication: Execute active campaigns and stakeholder workshops. - Innovation Culture: Run entrepreneurship training and mentoring sessions. - International Orientation: Facilitate first international collaboration projects.
<p>Scale-up and Consolidation (Q3 2027 – Q2 2028)</p>	<p>Expand successful pilots, strengthen networks, and deepen industry collaboration.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Digital Transformation: Scale up digital tools and solutions across wider SMEs and start-up base. - Green Transformation: Implement broader green innovation programs. - Stakeholder Communication: Enhance communication platforms with real-time feedback loops. - Innovation Culture: Integrate innovation best practices into organizational culture. - International Orientation: Expand participation in international consortia and funding programs.
<p>Evaluation and Strategy Revision (Q3 – Q4 2028)</p>	<p>Comprehensive review of outcomes, impact assessment, and update of strategic roadmap for next cycle.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evaluate all five initiatives' effectiveness. - Use stakeholder feedback to refine communication strategies. - Adjust training and mentorship programs based on impact. - Revise policies supporting digital and green transformation. - Plan for sustained international cooperation and knowledge exchange.

By anchoring the implementation in a time-bound structure with measurable milestones, the strategy promotes transparency, accountability, and adaptability, which are key conditions for long-term success in building a robust, innovative, and internationally competitive R&I ecosystem in Serbia.

6. Monitoring and Evaluation

Monitoring and evaluations assume the development of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for measuring the effectiveness of R&I Strategies at the Faculty and University Level. Both Universities and Faculties face strong pressures to contribute to economic and social development by improving their research and innovation activities. In this context, defining and monitoring KPIs is becoming increasingly important. KPIs represent a measurement tool that allows for tracking, assessing, and analysing results. In higher education, that is, at the level of Universities and Faculties, KPIs are used to gain insight into the progress of institutions, study programs, courses, as well as students in achieving set goals. It is important to emphasize that KPIs are not an end in themselves but serve as instruments for measuring achievements and evaluating success.

The developed set of indicators enables an objective evaluation of realized outcomes, identification of weaknesses, and guidance for future activities toward sustainable development and institutional positioning. For example, one of the indicators in higher education might be the number of enrolled students. If the Department of Business Management experiences a decline in enrolment in certain study programs, the defined KPI tracking the number of enrolled students per year can precisely identify when the decline occurred and its magnitude. Based on monitoring this indicator over a certain period, a decision can be made whether it is necessary to revise some study programs. In that case, the goal might be to increase the number of students by 20% within the next two years. Before setting this goal, it is essential to assess whether implementing it is financially justified and to form a team that will develop a strategy to increase student enrolment.

According to Watermark Insights, the phases in the development of KPIs for measuring the effectiveness of R&I strategies at the faculty and university level are systematized as follows>

- *Defining Strategic R&I Goals* - Establishing clear, precise, and ambitious goals is fundamental to selecting meaningful KPIs. These goals should embody faculties' or universities' overarching vision for research and innovation, including the pursuit of scientific excellence, technological advancement, impactful collaboration with industry, and positive societal contributions. Well-defining objectives serve as a guiding framework to ensure that KPIs align with institutional priorities and foster continuous progress.
- *Identification of Relevant Indicators* - This step involves the careful selection of KPIs that effectively capture both quantitative and qualitative dimensions of success. Key metrics typically include the number and influence of scientific publications, successful patent registrations, frequency and quality of collaborative projects, technology transfer activity, and the extent of external research funding. Incorporating qualitative aspects such as innovation impact, researcher satisfaction, and stakeholder engagement deepens the analytical perspective, ensuring a holistic appraisal of R&I performance.
- *Data Collection and Analysis* - Reliable KPI measurement hinges on systematic, ongoing data collection that emphasizes accuracy, relevance, and timeliness. Developing robust internal databases integrated with advanced software analytics tools enables institutions to monitor research and innovation activities in real time. This infrastructure supports transparent, data-driven decision-making processes that are essential for adaptive management and strategic foresight.
- *Setting Thresholds and Targets* - To render KPIs actionable, clearly defined benchmarks and success thresholds must be established. These typically include minimum acceptable levels, optimal performance standards, and exemplary targets that challenge the institution to excel. This stratification facilitates the early identification of performance gaps, directs resource allocation efficiently, and motivates continuous improvement across research and innovation endeavours.
- *Monitoring and Reporting* - Regular and transparent reporting is critical to fostering accountability and engagement among all institutional stakeholders. Tailored reports for

management, research teams, industry partners, and funding bodies support informed decision-making and promote alignment with strategic goals. Through consistent monitoring, institutions can track upward or downward trends, adjust tactics responsively, and celebrate achievements.

- *Evaluation and Revision of KPIs* - Given the dynamic nature of the research landscape, periodic review and recalibration of KPIs are imperative. This process ensures that performance indicators remain relevant, reflective of evolving institutional ambitions, scientific advances, and broader innovation trends. Responsive KPI management safeguards the continued utility of the measurement system and supports sustainable institutional growth.

Implementation of Improvement Measures - Insight gained from KPI analyses should translate into targeted action plans aimed at addressing identified weaknesses. This includes deploying support programs for researchers, upgrading research infrastructure, securing diversified funding streams, and cultivating stronger partnerships with external stakeholders. Such proactive interventions are vital for enhancing R&I capacity, elevating institutional reputation, and reinforcing competitive positioning.

The following will explain the key indicators that can be the starting point for assessing the success of the R&I strategy in higher education, i.e. at the university and faculty level:

1. Number of start-ups created.
2. Amount of funding raised by start-ups.
3. Number of patents filed and technologies commercialized.
4. Jobs created in innovative sectors.
5. Partnerships formed between academia and industry (number of signed contracts).
6. R&D expenditure relative to GDP, to improve position in international innovation rankings (Serbia is currently in 53rd position according to the OECD ranking).
7. Increase the number of commercially successful academic spin-offs by 20%.
8. Intensify participation in Horizon Europe programme.
9. Increase the proportion of graduates in science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM subjects) by 20%, and the proportion of women amongst graduates in technical subjects by 5%.
10. Create incentives for researchers to pursue entrepreneurial careers.

Number of Start-ups Created – An important indicator of the success of the research ecosystem is the number of start-up companies created as a result of research work, student projects, and collaboration with industry. This indicator measures the ability of universities and faculties to generate market-relevant ideas and support their realization through incubators and entrepreneurship support programs. Potential KPIs: annual number of start-ups founded originating from the academic community; Annual number of start-ups registered by students, researchers, and professors; Annual number of start-up ideas that received initial financial support from the faculty/university; Annual number of start-up teams that completed university entrepreneurship training programs.

Amount of Funds Raised by Start-ups – Financial resources obtained through grants, investments, or venture capital funds represent an important measure of start-up sustainability and market potential. Potential KPIs: total value of investments and grants secured yearly by start-ups affiliated with the university.

Number of Patent Applications – This indicator reflects the intensity of research activity and innovativeness. Potential KPIs: number of patent applications and number of licenses issued for use of university technologies annually; number of patents co-authored by faculty and collaborators; revenue generated from licenses and intellectual property rights.

Jobs Created in Innovation Centres – The university's contribution to employment in innovation centres can be measured through the number of jobs created directly or indirectly thanks to academic initiatives. Potential KPIs: number of jobs created in start-ups originating from the university; number

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of graduates employed in innovation companies within one year after graduation; number of university researchers who founded start-ups; number of joint university-industry projects resulting in employment; number of researchers engaged in innovation sectors through faculty programs.

Number of Agreements Signed with Industry – Signed agreements between faculties/universities and the private sector reflect the connection between academia and the real economy, enabling joint problem-solving. Potential KPIs: number of agreements signed between universities/faculties and industry annually; number of industry-funded projects implemented; number of professional practice agreements with the private sector; number of students who completed internships in institutions with signed agreements; number of students who received employment contracts after internships.

Share of Investment in R&D Relative to GDP – This represents an indicator of the innovativeness of the country and academic community, with the national goal being to improve the international standing. Potential KPIs: amount allocated for R&D at the university during budgeting processes.

Increase in the Number of Successful Academic Spin-off Companies - Measures the growth and impact of new enterprises created to commercialize research developed within universities. It reflects the institution's ability to foster entrepreneurship by transforming scientific knowledge into viable market solutions, contributing to job creation, economic development, and innovation ecosystems. Success is assessed not only by the number of spin-offs founded but also by their sustainability, funding attracted, job generation, and commercialization outcomes. Tracking this indicator helps universities evaluate and enhance their support structures, such as incubators and funding programs, ensuring that research outputs translate into tangible social and economic benefits.

Potential KPIs: number of approved projects and total funds attracted from Horizon Europe programs; Annual number of spin-offs founded originating from university research; Number of spin-offs surviving beyond a defined period (e.g., 3-5 years) to reflect sustainability; Total funding attracted by spin-offs through grants, venture capital, or other sources; Number of jobs created by spin-off companies; Revenue growth rate and profitability of spin-offs; Number of patents and licenses commercialized through spin-offs.

Participation in the Horizon Europe Program – This is a key framework for financing research projects at the European Union level. Participation of domestic researchers in this program demonstrates international competitiveness and collaboration capacity. Participation in the Horizon Europe Program is a key indicator of a university's engagement in international, collaborative research funded by the EU. It reflects the institution's ability to secure competitive funding, build partnerships across Europe, and contribute to high-impact projects addressing major societal challenges. Tracking this participation includes measuring approved projects, funding received, applications submitted, and researcher involvement. Active Horizon Europe participation demonstrates a university's research excellence, internationalization, and innovation capacity. Potential KPIs: number of approved projects and total funds drawn from Horizon Europe; number of university applications to Horizon projects annually; number of approved Horizon projects; number of faculty and researchers involved in Horizon projects; number of international partnerships established through Horizon Europe projects.

Increase the Proportion of Graduates in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) by 20%, and Increase the Proportion of Women Graduates in Technical Fields by 5% - measures an institution's commitment to expanding education and graduation rates in critical STEM fields, which are vital for fostering innovation, economic growth, and technological advancement. It also emphasizes improving gender diversity by increasing the representation of women in traditionally male-dominated technical disciplines. Tracking this indicator involves monitoring the total number and percentage of STEM graduates, as well as the share of female graduates in these fields. Achieving such targets reflects efforts to address workforce shortages in STEM, promote inclusivity and equal

opportunities, and prepare a diverse talent pool equipped for the demands of modern economies and research environments. This KPI highlights the institution's strategic focus on broadening participation and ensuring balanced representation in high-impact academic areas. Potential KPIs: number of STEM graduates annually; percentage of STEM graduates relative to total graduates; percentage of women graduates in technical and IT fields; number of scholarships and support programs for women in STEM; number of promotional activities organized to encourage women's enrolment in technical studies.

Incentives for Academic Entrepreneurship - measures how effectively a university fosters entrepreneurial activities among its researchers and academics by providing support mechanisms and motivational tools. It encompasses aspects such as participation in entrepreneurship training, availability of start-up funding through internal grants, collaboration with mentors and investors, and institutional policies that encourage commercialization and innovative ventures. Tracking this KPI reflects the institution's commitment to nurturing a culture of entrepreneurship, enabling researchers to translate their ideas into viable businesses, and ultimately enhancing technology transfer, innovation impact, and economic growth. Potential KPIs: number of researchers participating in entrepreneurship and knowledge commercialization training; number of projects submitted within university accelerators/innovation centres; number of internal calls for awarding startup grants to academic teams; number of collaborations with business mentors, funds, and investors supporting researchers; number of institutional measures (policies, awards, incentives) motivating researchers to start entrepreneurial initiatives.

Defining clear and measurable KPIs enables systematic monitoring of progress in the implementation of research and innovation strategies. Besides quantitative data, it is important to ensure the quality of the processes that lead to real innovations and long-term changes. By applying these indicators, universities in Serbia can contribute to strengthening national competitiveness, improving the innovation system, and creating knowledge with direct social and economic value. Establishing monitoring mechanisms at the national and regional levels entails the development and application of institutional, legal, and technical frameworks that allow for the systematic collection, analysis, and use of data for decision-making in the education sector. These mechanisms are crucial for ensuring transparency, accountability, and continuous improvement of education quality.

At the national level, monitoring involves defining KPIs (e.g., enrolment rates, graduation completion rates, graduate employment), assigning responsible bodies (e.g., ministries, statistical offices, accreditation agencies), and establishing reporting and evaluation intervals. At the regional level, monitoring includes adapting national indicators to local specificities, enabling a better understanding of challenges and needs at lower governance levels.

According to UNESCO (2017), monitoring and evaluation are integral parts of education policy because they enable measuring the effects of programs and interventions, identifying weaknesses, and making effective corrective measures. OECD (2021) emphasizes that well-designed monitoring mechanisms based on digital tools and a reliable, timely data base are key to building sustainable education systems.

For example, the European Commission, through tools such as the Education and Training Monitor, tracks the achievement of the goals of the European Education Area at the member state level, relying on indicators like early school leaving, basic skills achievements, student mobility, and participation in vocational education programs (European Commission, 2023). Implementing these mechanisms also implies involving various stakeholders (e.g., educational institutions, local governments, civil society, and the private sector), ensuring broader societal support and the validity of collected data (UNESCO IIEP, 2015).

7. Risk management

The EI Centre will adopt a structured and proactive approach to risk management to safeguard its objectives and long-term sustainability. This process will support informed decision-making, foster continuous innovation, and help identify emerging opportunities. Effective risk management is essential to maintaining the EI Centre’s operational integrity, credibility, and impact.

The EI Centre’s risk management framework will include the following key components:

- **Risk Identification** – Systematically recognize internal and external factors that may pose challenges to the EI Centre’s mission.
- **Risk Analysis** – Evaluate the likelihood and potential consequences of each identified risk.
- **Risk Evaluation** – Prioritize risks based on their severity and relevance, guiding resource allocation and strategic focus.
- **Risk Treatment** – Develop and implement appropriate responses to mitigate, transfer, avoid, or accept risks.
- **Monitoring and Review** – Regularly assess the effectiveness of risk mitigation strategies and adjust them as needed.

In recognition of the complex and uncertain environment surrounding entrepreneurship and innovation, the EI Centre will address risks across several dimensions, including strategic, operational, legal, and financial (Table 4). This integrated risk management process will enable the EI Centre to remain agile, resilient, and impactful in a dynamic ecosystem.

Table 4: Risk Matrix for the EI Centre

Risk category	Risk type	Likelihood of occurrence	Impact	Mitigation
Strategic	Misalignment with institutional, regional, or national strategy	Low	Low	Align EI Centre goals with university KPIs and national entrepreneurship and innovation strategies
	Policy or funding shifts at the institutional and national level	Medium	High	Diversify funding; engage in policy forums
Operational	Staff shortages or lack of capacity	Low	Medium	Cross-training, strategic hiring, partnerships with external experts
	Poor output and outcome delivery	Low	Medium	Regular quality review, screening, and feedback loops
	Low engagement from students or the community	Medium	Medium	Improve communication; co-create programs with target users
	Outdated or irrelevant curriculum or training	Low	Medium	Regular curriculum review based on trends and participant feedback
	Weak ecosystem partnerships or limited industry buy-in	Medium	Medium	Build strategic partnerships; host networking events; offer joint programming

Legal	Breach of intellectual property or legal disputes	Medium	Medium	Provide IP education; establish legal support and clear start-up agreements
Financial	Over-reliance on a single funding source	Medium	High	Develop income streams: grants, sponsorships, service revenue
	Misuse or mismanagement of funds	Low	Medium	Enforce financial controls, audits, and transparent reporting

8. Conclusion and Recommendations

This Action Plan strengthens Serbia’s research and innovation ecosystem by positioning the Faculty of Economics, University of Niš, as a central institutional actor. As a widening country, Serbia faces challenges such as limited infrastructure, insufficient access to finance, and weak collaboration between academia and industry. At the same time, it offers strong potential through an educated youth population, expanding digital connectivity, and access to European funding programs. The Plan aligns with Serbia’s Smart Specialisation Strategy, Horizon Europe, the European Green Deal, the Green Agenda for the Western Balkans, and the EU Digital Strategy, ensuring coherence with both national and European priorities. At its core stands the EI Centre, which supports start-up development, strengthens innovation and digital skills, and promotes collaboration among academia, industry, and international partners, turning research into practical solutions that bring social and economic value.

The strategic framework rests on three key pillars: research excellence, technology transfer, and innovative entrepreneurship. Achieving research excellence requires continuous investment in infrastructure and human capital, supported by universities, research institutes, and the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation. Translating knowledge into practice depends on strong intermediary institutions, such as Technology Transfer Offices and innovation centres, which connect academic research with the needs of the market. The Innovation Fund and the Development Agency of Serbia further advance innovative entrepreneurship by providing financial assistance, mentorship, and incubation programs. Through the combined impact of these efforts, Serbia builds the foundation for a resilient and competitive national innovation ecosystem.

Effective implementation relies on strong coordination among institutions, consistent policies, and well-designed initiatives that lead to measurable progress. At the national level, governance is guided by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation, supported by the Innovation Fund, the Science Fund, and the Development Agency of Serbia. Their joint efforts are reinforced by a growing network of technology parks, incubators, and innovation centres that connect research, entrepreneurship, and policy within a European framework. Strategic direction comes from national documents such as The Power of Knowledge (2021–2025), the upcoming Strategy for Scientific and Technological Development 2025–2029, and the Smart Specialisation Strategy 2020–2027, which together provide coherence and long-term vision for research and innovation in Serbia.

Within this ecosystem, universities occupy a central position as creators and transmitters of knowledge. The University of Niš, through the Faculty of Economics and its EI Centre, will strengthen links between science and business, promote international collaboration, and foster cultural change through educational, digital, and green initiatives that expand local innovation capacity to the European level. Collaboration among these actors, including ministries, research institutions,

businesses, investors, and intermediary organizations, will create a dynamic and interconnected system that supports sustainable growth and competitiveness.

Implementation will follow a structured five-phase timeline from 2026 to 2028, coordinated by the Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation. The phases include capacity building, institutionalization, implementation, scale-up, and evaluation, each focusing on developing skills, mentorship, and collaboration with business and academic partners. Regular milestone tracking and semi-annual reporting will ensure accountability and continuous improvement, while maintaining alignment with national and European objectives.

To monitor progress and evaluate the impact of these activities, a set of KPIs has been introduced. They measure the effectiveness of research and innovation initiatives through outcomes such as the number of start-ups created, patents filed, partnerships between academia and industry, and participation in international programs such as Horizon Europe. Additional indicators emphasize the growth of academic spin-offs, increased investment in research and development, and greater inclusion of women and youth in science and technology.

Additionally, the EI Centre applies a comprehensive risk management framework that identifies, assesses, and mitigates strategic, operational, legal, and financial risks. By maintaining alignment with institutional and national strategies, diversifying funding, and reviewing results regularly, the Centre strengthens its resilience and capacity to operate effectively in a changing environment.

Based on the findings and analysis, several recommendations emerge. Strengthening coordination among all actors in the innovation ecosystem remains essential to ensure that goals, resources, and activities are effectively aligned. The Faculty of Economics, through the work of the EI Centre, should continue expanding international partnerships and participation in European research programs to enhance visibility and access to funding. Greater emphasis should be placed on fostering an inclusive and dynamic entrepreneurial environment through targeted support, mentorship, and collaboration opportunities. Continuous professional development in digital and green competencies should become an integral part of all academic and entrepreneurial activities. Finally, communicating achievements and good practices in research and innovation will help build trust, inspire participation, and highlight the societal value of innovation.

Through coordinated institutional efforts, structured implementation, transparent monitoring, and proactive risk management, this Action Plan provides a coherent roadmap for sustainable growth. The integration of research excellence, entrepreneurship, and international cooperation through the EI Centre strengthens Serbia's capacity to advance toward a knowledge-based, competitive, and inclusive European innovation landscape.

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ACTION PLANS FOR R&I STRATEGY IMPLEMENTATION, FEUT, ALBANIA

1. Execution Summary

Albania is classified as a “developing innovator”, with innovation performance at around 42% of the EU average. This reflects both persistent challenges—fragmented cooperation, limited R&D funding, weak university–industry collaboration—and important opportunities, including a young population, growing digitalisation and access to EU and regional funding instruments. Within this context, the Faculty of Economy, University of Tirana (FEUT) has prepared a Research & Innovation (R&I) Strategy on Sustainable Entrepreneurship, aligned with:

- The Development Strategy of the University of Tirana 2023–2028, which places research, innovation and internationalisation at the core of institutional development;
- The National Strategy for Scientific Research, Technology and Innovation 2023–2030;
- The European Research Area (ERA), Horizon Europe and the European Green Agenda for the Western Balkans.

The present Action Plan is the key implementation instrument of FEUT’s on R&I Sustainable Entrepreneurship. Its purpose is to translate the strategic vision and three pillars—research excellence, technology transfer and exploitation, and innovative/sustainable entrepreneurship—into a coherent set of concrete, time-bound and measurable actions for the period 2026–2028. The Plan focuses particularly on:

- Building a culture of sustainable and innovative entrepreneurship among students, staff and partners;
- Strengthening research and teaching in climate, environmental sustainability and green transition;
- Enhancing collaboration with businesses, public institutions and civil society through a quadruple-helix approach;
- Supporting Albania’s progress towards a knowledge-based, green and inclusive economy and its EU integration path.

Implementation will follow a structured five-phase timeline from 2026 to 2028, coordinated by FEUT leadership and a dedicated Sustainable Entrepreneurship & Innovation Coordination Group (representatives of USEIPM Project).

2. Key Pillars of the R&I Strategy

The present Action Plan operationalises these three pillars, with special emphasis on sustainable entrepreneurship, environmental sustainability in teaching and research, and student-centred initiatives.

2.1. Research Excellence

Within the first pillar, Research Excellence, FEUT aims to improve the quality, relevance and impact of its research in line with national and EU priorities, particularly the green transition, digital economy and inclusive growth. Demonstrating and increasing the research excellence at FEUT requires continuous investment in infrastructure, services and collaborative environments, as well as a strong research culture. The aim is to support researchers across all career stages by fostering interdisciplinary work, enhancing PhD programmes, increasing international and national funded

projects and attracting international partners. Additionally, the aim is to increase collaboration with industry through joint projects. By making innovation and community work a natural part of research, FEUT will help ensure that its results bring really social and economic benefits in Albania and beyond.

2.2. Technology Transfer and Exploitation

The second pillar focuses on translating research results into practical solutions and services for the economy and society. Priority actions include strengthening liaison and project offices, intensifying collaborative projects with firms and public bodies, supporting start-up creation based on staff and student expertise, and using living labs and pilot projects to test innovations with real users.

2.3. Innovative Entrepreneurship

The third pillar develops entrepreneurial mindsets and ventures within FEUT and its ecosystem, integrating entrepreneurship and innovation management into curricula, supporting both traditional and innovative business ideas, and promoting digital, green and social entrepreneurship.

3. Strategic enablers and key initiatives

To develop research and innovation at the Faculty of Economy (FEUT), we need not only clear goals but also the basic conditions that make them possible. These conditions include good governance and coordination, alignment with national and EU policies, and strong support for staff and students.

In this chapter we look at:

- how UT and FEUT are governed and linked to national strategies,
- the specific role of universities in Albania's innovation system, and
- the main areas where we will act: cultural change, international cooperation, communication with stakeholders, digital transformation and the green transition.

Together, these elements will help to build a more open, collaborative and competitive research and innovation environment in Albania that supports development and EU integration.

3.1. Governance

In Albania, research and innovation are guided at national level by the Ministry of Education and Sports (MES), based on Law 80/2015 "On Higher Education and Scientific Research in Higher Education Institutions" and the newer National Strategy for Science, Technology and Innovation 2023–2030. MES sets overall policy, aligns national priorities with the European Research Area and EU accession agenda, and coordinates reforms in higher education and research.

The main funding and implementation body is the National Agency for Scientific Research and Innovation (NASRI/AKKSHI). NASRI evaluates and finances research and infrastructure projects, supports technology and innovation programmes, and acts as the national contact point for Horizon Europe, COST and other international schemes, with a specific mandate to strengthen links between universities, business and government.

Other national actors also influence the R&I ecosystem, including the Inter-ministerial Committee for Smart Specialisation, the National S3 Team, and agencies responsible for statistics,

industrial property and digitalisation. Together they help coordinate measures for human capital, research infrastructure, open science and knowledge transfer across sectors.

Within this governance system, UT and in particular FEUT, plays a central role. UT is the largest public university in the country and holds the “HR Excellence in Research” (HRS4R) label from the European Commission, recognising its commitment to improving research careers and working conditions. FEUT contributes to national priorities through its academic staff, doctoral programmes and EU-funded projects in economics, business, governance and sustainable development, and acts as a key partner for NASRI, ministries and international donors.

3.2. National R&I Strategy

Albania’s main policy framework for research and innovation is the National Strategy for Science, Technology and Innovation 2023–2030. The strategy aims to strengthen research institutions, modernise infrastructure, increase international cooperation and raise the contribution of science and innovation to economic growth and social well-being. It emphasises alignment with the European Research Area, greater participation in Horizon Europe, and better use of research results in public policy and the private sector.

A second key pillar is the National Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) 2025–2030, approved by the Council of Ministers in December 2024. S3 identifies three main priority domains for future investment and innovation: (i) renewable energy and natural resources, (ii) sustainable and diversified tourism, and (iii) a healthy and sustainable food chain, supported by cross-cutting measures for human capital, digitalisation and an innovation-friendly business environment.

These national strategies provide the framework within which UT and FEUT design their own research and innovation agendas. FEUT’s focus on green transition, digital economy, entrepreneurship and inclusive growth directly supports S3 priorities and the STI 2023–2030 objectives. Through interdisciplinary research groups, doctoral training, technology-transfer activities and collaboration with business and public institutions, FEUT helps translate national strategic goals into concrete projects, partnerships and policy inputs at university and faculty level.

3.3. Universities

The country has public universities and private higher education institutions, with the public University of Tirana (UT) as the largest and most comprehensive. Over the last years, Albania’s research performance has improved: the European Innovation Scoreboard 2024 reports strong growth in the “attractiveness of research systems”, driven in part by an increase in highly cited publications.

Within this landscape, UT – and the Faculty of Economy (FEUT) in particular – is a leading hub of scientific output and international cooperation. UT is among the top Albanian beneficiaries of EU research funds, with more than €1.6 million in net EU contributions from programmes such as Horizon 2020 and Erasmus+. According to the ERA Country Report 2024, Albania’s participation in Horizon Europe has also increased: the number of participating institutions rose from 26 to 36 between 2021 and 2024, and the associated project budget from €5 million to €6.8 million.¹ These trends reflect a gradual strengthening of the university research base and its international connections.

¹ <https://westernbalkans-infohub.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/08/ERA-Country-Report-2024-Albania>.

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The role of universities, and especially UT/FEUT, in implementing the R&I agenda can be seen in four main dimensions:

- **Centres of knowledge production.** Universities lead basic and applied research in economics, business, governance, digitalisation and sustainability. Through academic projects and publications, they generate new knowledge that underpins innovation and evidence-based policy in Albania²
- **Bridges to industry and society.** Universities increasingly cooperate with businesses, public institutions and NGOs through joint projects, consulting, internships and living-lab initiatives. FEUT's work with ministries, municipalities, banks and enterprises on topics such as entrepreneurship, green transition and digital skills helps transfer knowledge into practice and supports regional development.³
- **Gateways to European programmes.** Through participation in Horizon Europe, Erasmus+, COST and other schemes, Albanian universities bring European standards, methods and networks into the national system. This exchange raises research quality and opens new opportunities for students and staff, while aligning Albania with the European Research Area.
- **Support for public policy and strategic planning.** Academic experts contribute to national strategies such as the STI Strategy 2023–2030 and the Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) by providing analysis, data and policy advice. FEUT's expertise in economics and public policy is particularly important for designing reforms in areas like innovation funding, entrepreneurship support and EU integration

3.4. Cultural change

The national start-up and innovation ecosystem is still considered “nascent” and among the weaker in Europe, with low levels of innovation capability and entrepreneurial skills, especially among young people. Building a stronger innovation culture therefore requires coordinated action by universities, businesses, government and civil society.

At the policy level, recent measures such as Law No. 25/2022 “On the Support and Development of Start-ups” and its 2023 amendments signal a growing recognition of entrepreneurship as a strategic priority. These laws establish a dedicated framework for start-up registration, incentives and support services, and are complemented by programmes like “EU for Innovation” and new initiatives of the EIT Community Hub, which aim to strengthen local innovation communities, mentor young founders and connect Albania to European networks.

Universities, including UT and FEUT, are gradually integrating entrepreneurship and innovation into teaching and student life through competitions, hackathons, incubator collaborations, career services and project-based learning. Systematically involving students in these activities at all levels of study helps normalise creativity, risk-taking and problem-solving as core skills, and encourages them to see self-employment and start-ups as realistic career paths. Formal recognition of knowledge transfer and third-mission activities in academic careers—together with clearer incentives for staff and students who engage with companies, public bodies and NGOs—would further strengthen this shift.

²https://dig.watch/resource/albanias-national-strategy-for-scientific-research-technology-and-innovation-2023-2030?utm_source.com

³https://1future.feut.edu.al/wpcontent/uploads/2023/06/15.1Future_NASRI_R_D_Ecosystem.pdf?utm_source.com

For businesses and the public sector, cultural change means treating innovation and collaboration with universities not as one-off projects, but as long-term investments. EU-supported schemes that co-finance collaborative R&I projects, local innovation programmes in municipalities, and public procurement that favours innovative solutions can all reinforce this behaviour. Finally, communication campaigns and visibility for successful Albanian start-ups, researchers and social innovators—especially youth-led initiatives—are essential to build public trust in innovation and to inspire a more entrepreneurial mindset across society

3.5. International orientation

The Objective of International orientation is to strengthen universities international profile and cooperation in sustainable entrepreneurship and R&I. In this regard the key actions are related to: Expand participation in Horizon Europe, Erasmus+ and COST projects related to green transition, digital transformation and entrepreneurship; Use COIL (Collaborative Online International Learning) and joint modules to expose students to international cases of sustainable entrepreneurship; Engage Albanian diaspora experts as mentors, guest lecturers and partners in FEUT R&I and entrepreneurship activities. The aim is to increase: the number of international projects with a sustainable entrepreneurship component; number of joint international activities per academic year; and Number of diaspora experts involved to bring new perspectives and best experiences.

3.6. Stakeholders' communication

To strengthen the role of FEUT in Albania's research and innovation ecosystem, it is important to improve how results and activities are communicated to both internal and external stakeholders. FEUT promotes project results and activities on its website, where projects, partners, courses, events and key indicators are presented in a clear and accessible way. This will be complemented by a dedicated "Sustainable Entrepreneurship at FEUT" communication activity by using social media, podcasts, etc to highlight student and staff achievements and to share good practices. In addition, progress in this area will be monitored through the regular update of the online dashboard (at least twice per year), the number and reach of communication products produced, and participation levels at the stakeholders' forum.

4. Roles and responsibilities

The effective implementation of FEUT's Action Plan on Sustainable Entrepreneurship and R&I requires a clear allocation of roles and responsibilities among all key actors in Albania's innovation ecosystem. In a context characterised by multiple institutions, emerging programmes and evolving partnerships, coordinated collaboration is essential to avoid fragmentation, ensure efficient use of resources and maximise impact. Clearly defined responsibilities enhance transparency, accountability and trust, while also helping to align local initiatives at FEUT with national and European priorities.

Government and public institutions provide the overall strategic and regulatory framework. The Ministry of Education and Sports (MES) is responsible for higher education and research policy, aligning national priorities with the European Research Area and the EU accession agenda. It oversees the implementation of the National Strategy for Science, Technology and Innovation 2023–2030 and ensures that universities contribute to national development goals. The Inter-ministerial Committee for Smart Specialisation and the National S3 Team further coordinate horizontal measures for human

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capital, research infrastructure, digitalisation and innovation-friendly business environments, providing the strategic context in which FEUT's actions take place.

The National Agency for Scientific Research and Innovation (NASRI/AKKSHI) is the key funding and implementation body for research and innovation programmes. Its roles include evaluating and financing research and infrastructure projects, supporting technology and innovation schemes, and acting as the national contact point for Horizon Europe, COST and other international initiatives. By prioritising projects that foster university–industry collaboration, green transition and digital transformation, NASRI helps to create opportunities that FEUT and its partners can leverage through this Action Plan. Other specialised agencies responsible for statistics, industrial property and digitalisation support evidence-based policymaking, protection of intellectual property, and the expansion of digital services that enable innovation.

Universities and research institutions are central to knowledge generation and human-capital development. The University of Tirana (UT), as the largest public university and holder of the “HR Excellence in Research” (HRS4R) label, has a particular responsibility to set quality standards in research careers and working conditions. Within UT, the Faculty of Economy (FEUT) is a key actor in economics, business, governance and sustainable development. FEUT's responsibilities include conducting high-quality research aligned with national strategies and Smart Specialisation priorities, integrating sustainable entrepreneurship and innovation into curricula, and engaging students and staff in projects that address real socio-economic challenges. Academic staff and doctoral candidates contribute through interdisciplinary research groups, policy analyses and participation in international programmes such as Horizon Europe and Erasmus+.

Within FEUT, institutional leadership (Dean's Office, departmental heads) and the Sustainable Entrepreneurship & Innovation Coordination Group (established within the USE IPM project) play an operational coordination role. They are responsible for planning and sequencing activities across the four phases of implementation, monitoring progress against milestones, and ensuring that teaching, research and third-mission activities are mutually reinforcing. Their tasks include facilitating internal communication, mobilising staff and students for participation in pilots and living labs, and maintaining links with NASRI, ministries, municipalities and international partners.

Entrepreneurs, start-ups and small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are crucial for turning research and education outputs into concrete innovations. Start-ups and spin-offs emerging from student and staff projects give practical shape to sustainable and digital entrepreneurship ambitions, while established SMEs test and adopt new solutions developed in collaboration with FEUT. Their responsibilities include engaging in joint projects, providing real business cases for teaching and student theses, mentoring young entrepreneurs, and co-creating sustainability-oriented business models in areas such as tourism, renewable energy and agri-food. In turn, FEUT supports these actors through idea labs, business competitions, consulting projects and access to trained graduates.

Investors and financial institutions provide the financial backbone that enables innovation to scale. Commercial banks, development finance institutions, business angels and venture capital funds are responsible for assessing and supporting promising sustainable and digital business ideas. Their collaboration with FEUT may include participation in juries for business-plan competitions, offering tailored financial products for early-stage ventures, and co-designing financial literacy and investment-readiness training. By engaging with FEUT's ecosystem, investors gain access to a pipeline of projects, while helping guide teams towards viable, responsible and growth-oriented models.

Innovation infrastructure and intermediary organisations help connect these actors. Incubators, technology and innovation hubs, co-working spaces and municipal development offices provide physical and organisational platforms where students, researchers, entrepreneurs and public officials can test ideas, build partnerships and access support services. Their responsibilities include hosting events, providing mentoring and networking opportunities, and facilitating access to local

communities and markets. In many cases, they act as practical implementation partners for FEUT’s living labs, student consulting projects and sustainability-focused pilot initiatives.

Finally, policymakers and international partners shape the broader environment in which FEUT’s Action Plan is implemented. National and local policymakers are responsible for ensuring that regulatory frameworks, public procurement practices and support schemes enable experimentation, collaboration and sustainable innovation. International partners—including the European Commission, EU-funded programmes (such as “EU for Innovation”), the EIT Community, UNESCO and other donors—provide technical assistance, funding opportunities and access to European and global networks. Members of the Albanian diaspora, acting as mentors, guest lecturers and project partners, further enrich the ecosystem with external expertise and international perspectives.

Through clearly defined and complementary roles, these stakeholders form an interconnected system capable of supporting sustainable entrepreneurship and innovation in Albania. The successful implementation of FEUT’s Action Plan depends on their coordinated action, regular communication and shared commitment to green and digital transitions. By building strong, long-term partnerships between government, universities, businesses, investors, civil society and international actors, Albania can accelerate its progress toward a knowledge-based, inclusive and competitive innovation economy.

As defined in the strategic document, the Strategic Priorities will be focused on:

- Improving pathways for knowledge and technology exchange between universities, businesses, and public institutions, helping research outcomes transition more smoothly into practical use and commercialisation.
- Cultivating a proactive and innovative mindset among students and researchers, with an emphasis on designing solutions that integrate sustainability from the outset.
- Supporting the growth of responsible and sustainability-oriented business initiatives, encouraging researchers and students to embed environmental and social considerations into their entrepreneurial ideas.
- Strengthening the interpersonal and professional competencies of academics and emerging entrepreneurs, ensuring they possess the communication, leadership, and collaborative skills needed to thrive in contemporary innovation environments.
- Expanding cooperation across academic disciplines and external sectors, creating stronger links between education, research, industry, and community actors to reinforce a vibrant innovation ecosystem.
- Encouraging the transformation of research findings into real-world applications, motivating the creation of new services, solutions, and technologies that address societal needs and contribute to national development.
- Nurturing an environment where experimentation, co-creation, and continuous improvement are integral, empowering students and researchers to engage meaningfully with external stakeholders and actively participate in shaping innovation processes.

5. Timeline and Milestones

1. Phase 1- Foundation Q1 to Q4 2026

Phase	Timeline	Strategic priority	Key activities	Focus
Phase 1 – Foundation	Q1–Q2 2026	Improving pathways for knowledge and	Map existing collaboration (MoUs, projects, internships)	Mapping & governance

		technology exchange		
Phase 1 – Foundation	Q1–Q4 2026	Cultivating a proactive and innovative mindset	Integrate basic innovation and entrepreneurship content into core courses; run 1–2 awareness events per semester (talks, case-study).	Awareness & curriculum
Phase 1 – Foundation	Q3–Q4 2026	Cultivating a proactive and innovative mindset	Launch a small “idea lab” or challenge for students and young researchers focused on sustainability-oriented solutions.	Early experimentation
Phase 1 – Foundation	Q4 2026	Supporting responsible, sustainability-oriented business initiatives	Pilot one sustainability-focused business idea competition with mentoring from external experts.	First pilots
Phase 1 – Foundation	Q1–Q2 2026	Strengthening interpersonal and professional competencies	Identify key transversal skills (communication, leadership, teamwork, project management); design short workshops for students and early-career researchers.	Skills framework
Phase 1 – Foundation	Q2–Q4 2026	Expanding cooperation across disciplines and sectors	Set up 2–3 interdisciplinary working groups (e.g. sustainable tourism, green finance, digital business); organise at least one internal “innovation day” bringing together researchers and external stakeholders.	Internal networking
Phase 1 – Foundation	Q2–Q4 2026	Nurturing experimentation and co-creation	Define the concept for FEUT living labs / co-creation spaces; choose 1–2 pilot themes (e.g. sustainable campus, green SMEs).	Concept & pilots

2. Phase 2: Pilot & Early Implementation Q1-Q4 2027

Phase	Timeline	Strategic priority	Key activities	Focus
Phase 2 – Pilot & Early Implementation	Q1–Q4 2027	Improving pathways for knowledge and technology exchange	Discuss regular “research–business–policy” matchmaking events; pilot at least 2 collaboration projects (student consulting, joint research, policy studies).	Operational partnerships

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Phase 2 – Pilot & Early Implementation	Q1–Q4 2027	Strengthening interpersonal and professional competencies	Institutionalise skills training (include in elective modules, , PhD training); introduce mentoring/buddy systems pairing students with alumni and practitioners.	Capacity building
Phase 2 – Pilot & Early Implementation	Q1–Q4 2027	Expanding cooperation across disciplines and sectors	Run joint projects within interdisciplinary groups (student theses, applied research with municipalities/companies); focused on sustainable innovation.	Cross-sector projects
Phase 2 – Pilot & Early Implementation	Q1–Q4 2027	Encouraging transformation of research into applications	Support preparation of policy briefs from selected research outputs;	Policy briefs

3. Phase 3: Scale up Q1-Q2 2028

Phase	Timeline	Strategic priority	Key activities	Focus
Phase 3 – Scale-up	Q1–Q2 2028	Improving pathways for knowledge and technology exchange	Formalise collaboration models that worked best (framework agreements, advisory groups); document success stories and lessons learned.	Institutionalisation
Phase 3 – Scale-up	Q1–Q2 2028	Cultivating a proactive and innovative mindset	Extend project-based and challenge-based learning to more programmes; integrate innovation and sustainability learning outcomes into students’ activities	Mainstreaming
Phase 3 – Scale-up	Q1–Q2 2028	Strengthening interpersonal and professional competencies	Embed transversal-skills training into career services and doctoral schools; track participation and feedback to refine content.	Consolidation
Phase 3 – Scale-up	Q1–Q2 2028	Nurturing experimentation and co-creation	Expand living-lab activities to new themes; integrate co-creation components into at least 3 workshops.	Wider adoption

4. Phase 4: Consolidation and Evaluation Q3-Q4 2028

Phase	Timeline	Strategic priority	Key activities	Focus
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Phase 4 – Consolidation & Evaluation	Q3–Q4 2028	All strategic priorities	Evaluate progress on indicators for each priority (pathways, mindset, responsible business, skills, cooperation,); collect qualitative feedback from stakeholders and students.	Evaluation
Phase 4 – Consolidation & Evaluation	Q3–Q4 2028	All strategic priorities	Identify practices to be fully institutionalised (regulations, centres, annual events); integrate them into the next FEUT R&I and sustainable-entrepreneurship strategy.	Integration & next cycle
Phase 4 – Consolidation & Evaluation	Q3–Q4 2028	All strategic priorities	Prepare a stakeholder workshop summarising result, success stories and remaining gaps; use findings to design funding proposals and partnerships for 2029+.	Learning & future planning

6. Monitoring and Evaluation

- Annual Implementation Report prepared by working group and validated by FEUT;
- Mid-term review at the end of 2027;
- Final evaluation in Q4 2028, including recommendations for the next strategy period.

7. Risk management

- **Operational risks** – Staff shortages, low student engagement, fragmented internal coordination, outdated curricula.
 - *Mitigation:* Capacity-building, cross-training, incentives for staff and students, regular curriculum review.
- **Legal risks** – data protection issues (research data, survey information).
 - *Mitigation:* Legal support for contracts, compliant data management procedures.

8. Conclusion and Recommendations

This Action Plan operationalises FEUT’s R&I Strategy on Sustainable Entrepreneurship by providing a concrete roadmap for 2026–2028. It connects high-level strategic objectives with specific activities, timelines, responsibilities and indicators. Key recommendations for successful implementation include:

1. **Strong institutional commitment:** Ensure that sustainable entrepreneurship and R&I are treated as core priorities in UT and FEUT decision-making.
2. **Integrated approach:** Combine research, teaching and third-mission activities through living labs, policy briefs and student projects tackling real local challenges.
3. **Quadruple-helix cooperation:** Engage businesses, public authorities, civil society and the Albanian diaspora as partners, not just beneficiaries.

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4. **Focus on green and digital transition:** Use sustainable entrepreneurship education and research to support Albania's green and digital transformation in line with EU priorities and SDGs.

5. **Robust monitoring and learning:** to learn, adapt and continuously improve the Action Plan.

Through coordinated efforts, transparent monitoring and proactive risk management, FEUT can strengthen its role as a driver of sustainable entrepreneurship and innovation in Albania, contributing to a more competitive, inclusive and green European future.

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ACTION PLANS FOR R&I STRATEGY IMPLEMENTATION, FEUSK, NORTH MACEDONIA

1. Executive Summary

This Action Plan operationalizes the Research & Innovation (R&I) Strategy by translating five strategic pillars into a **sequenced implementation roadmap (2026–2028)** with clear programmes, stakeholders, timelines, milestones, and KPIs. It is designed to support the gradual maturation of the **University Entrepreneurship and Innovation Centre (UEIC)** and the wider national ecosystem—moving from foundational institutional set-up, through ecosystem expansion and integration, to measurable impact and systemic consolidation. At the core of the Plan is the positioning of UEIC as the system’s **“front door” and operational connector**: coordinating delivery across faculties, research institutes and laboratories; running structured services such as *grant-to-impact* support, **labs-as-a-service**, the entrepreneurship pipeline, and stakeholder engagement; and maintaining a performance and impact evidence system through dashboards and annual reporting. The Action Plan addresses fragmentation by ensuring that partnerships become implementable pipelines (not only MoUs), and that progress is demonstrated through **quantitative indicators plus qualitative, externally validated evidence**.

Implementation is organized around **five pillars**. Pillar 1 strengthens **research excellence aligned with Smart Specialisation (S3)** through targeted support for PhD/Industrial PhD/PostDoc pipelines, modernized shared infrastructure, applied “lighthouse” programmes for green and digital transformation, and internationalisation via Horizon Europe/COST/EUREKA and European research infrastructures. Pillar 2 professionalizes **technology transfer, IP and knowledge valorisation** by establishing **TTO as a one-stop shop**, streamlining disclosure-to-decision processes, and deploying standardized templates and faster procedures to reduce time and transaction costs. Pillar 3 builds **highly innovative entrepreneurship** through a staged pathway (idea → pre-incubation → incubation → acceleration → scaling), strengthened mentoring (including alumni/diaspora), and investment readiness linked to banks, angels, VC and IFIs. Pillar 4 embeds **ecosystem networking and internationalisation** through a Quadruple-Helix Advisory Board, formal operational partnerships with ministries/agencies, municipalities, chambers and clusters, and structured EU integration channels including EIT networks. Pillar 5 ensures the whole system “works in practice” via **CoARA-aligned assessment and impact measurement**, combining discipline-sensitive rubrics, narrative evidence formats

Delivery is phased to match realistic capacity-building. **Phase 1 (Foundation, Q1 2026–Q2 2027)** focuses on establishing governance, launching and staffing the TTO, initiating priority lab upgrades into shared services, adopting CoARA-aligned assessment tools (including narrative CV formats), and starting targeted doctoral and postdoctoral programmes aligned with S3 domains. **Phase 2 (Expansion, Q3 2027–Q4 2027)** scales implementation: labs-as-a-service fully operational, cooperation instruments (innovation vouchers, collaborative grants, industrial PhDs) active, entrepreneurship pipeline running with mentors and finance connections, and stronger international project participation supported by improved grant-to-impact services. **Phase 3 (Maturation, Q1 2028–Q4 2028)** shifts toward results and consolidation: a fully operational KPI dashboard, an annual CoARA-aligned UEIC Impact Report backed by external validation, increased commercialization outcomes (licenses, spin-offs, contract research), and stronger EU integration performance (proposal success rates, mobility, partnerships).

Finally, the Action Plan embeds a robust Monitoring & Evaluation logic and risk-informed management so that implementation remains adaptive. Success by 2028 is expected to be visible in stronger shared research capacity, improved TT/IP performance, a functioning start-up/spin-off

pipeline with capital attraction, higher EU programme participation and success, and credible public value demonstrated through balanced KPIs and verified impact evidence.

2. Key Pillars of the R&I Strategy

The Strategy applies a comprehensive approach to research and innovation excellence, strengthening the ecosystem through **five strategic pillars** and cross-cutting reforms. Each pillar combines (i) a clear purpose, (ii) CoARA-aligned assessment logic, and (iii) practical programmes/actions that move results from research to impact.

2.1. Research Excellence

Purpose. Strengthen excellence in the domains of the Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) by investing in research human resources, research centres, infrastructure, and internationalisation.

Key programmes/actions (condensed):

- **Human resources for R&D:** structured support for PhDs, Industrial PhDs and PostDocs, including placements/cooperation with companies and public sector in S3 priority areas; joint academic–industry supervision; doctoral school modules on innovation, entrepreneurship and project management.
- **Modernised infrastructure + open/shared access:** upgrade laboratories/equipment and establish “common access” via a service model and catalogue for SMEs/start-ups/industry, with transparent access rules and Service-Level Agreements (SLAs).
- **Applied research for green and digital transformation:** portfolio of projects oriented toward prototypes, testing and pilots; “lighthouse” programmes co-defined with partners and updated through annual thematic challenge briefs to keep topics demand-oriented.
- **Internationalisation:** systemic support for participation in Horizon Europe, COST and EUREKA and integration in European infrastructures and consortia via partnerships and mobility.

2.2. Technology Transfer and Exploitation

Purpose. Strengthen commercialisation by professionalising processes and reducing IP barriers.

Key programmes/actions (condensed):

- **UEIC Technology Transfer Office (TTO) as a “one-stop shop”:** a single front door for companies, researchers and investors covering collaboration, contract research, IP procedures, licensing and spin-off formation; includes IP clinics, model contracts (NDA, MTA, licensing/option agreements) and standard rules for revenue sharing and equity participation.
- **Standing IP Committee + faster decisions:** time-bound decisions on protection, ownership and route to market, with conflict-of-interest management.
- **Simplified IP management and clear “valorisation path”:** disclosure by researchers → rapid novelty and freedom-to-operate checks → short market screening → IP decision (patent/utility model vs know-how vs open access) → route selection (licence or spin-off).
- **Academia–industry cooperation instruments:** activation of innovation vouchers, collaborative grants and industrial PhDs to accelerate joint R&I and commercialisation.

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2.3. Innovative entrepreneurship

Purpose. Build a pipeline for knowledge-based companies that can attract funding and scale to global markets.

Key programmes/actions (condensed):

- **Entrepreneurial path from idea to growth:** a staged process from ideation/verification → pre-incubation → incubation → acceleration/market entry → scaling/internationalisation, with criteria and support at each step.
- **Mentoring + alumni/diaspora bridge:** a structured mentor base (entrepreneurs, industry experts, investors), cohort milestones, and diaspora links for international markets, knowledge and contacts; cooperation with regional accelerators and EIT KICs to refine business models and prepare investor pitches.
- **Investment readiness + finance connections:** dedicated investment-readiness coaching and systematic connection to grants, banks, business angels and VC funds, including co-investment frameworks and standard instruments (e.g., convertible notes).
- **SME Academy (executive education):** micro-credentials (finance, export, digital/green skills) and applied clinics that channel promising SME initiatives to lab vouchers and PoC calls.

2.4. Ecosystem Networking and Internationalization

Purpose. Keep UEIC permanently connected at all levels and functioning as a practical coordination node for the ecosystem.

Key programmes/actions (condensed):

- **Quadruple-helix Advisory Board:** regular meetings with university, business, public institutions and civil society to co-define priorities, propose thematic challenges and monitor progress.
- **Formal partnerships + operational protocols:** memoranda and working arrangements with ministries/agencies, municipalities, chambers and clusters to deliver joint projects, pilots, contract research and innovation support for firms.
- **EU integration via programmes and networks:** structured support for Horizon Europe participation and use of EIT communities/accelerator networks to access partnerships, expertise and funding for market-oriented projects.

2.5. CoARA reform for qualitative assessment and impact indicators

Purpose. Ensure all pillars work in practice through a CoARA-compliant system combining qualitative evidence and responsible metrics to measure UEIC impact transparently.

Key programmes/actions (condensed):

- **Assessment policy + rubrics:** shift evaluation toward quality, integrity, openness, collaboration and impact, using discipline-sensitive rubrics across research, TT/IP, entrepreneurship and engagement.
- **Narrative evidence formats:** standardized Impact/Innovation/Collaboration cases with contribution statements and verifiable evidence (links, prototypes, partner proof).
- **Balanced KPI scorecard:** track capacity → process quality → outputs → outcomes/impact while avoiding JIF/h-index as decision rules.

- **Open science, stakeholder validation and reporting:** integrate DMPs, open access and ethics/governance checks; collect external validation and partner surveys; and publish an annual UEIC impact report backed by a digital dashboard.

3. Strategic Enablers and Key Initiatives

In a widening/low-resource context—characterised by fragmented financing, limited modern infrastructure, and a relatively small research workforce—these enablers are not “add-ons”, but the core conditions for delivery at scale.

3.1. Governance

A robust governance set-up ensures decisions are fast, transparent, and aligned with national priorities and stakeholder needs, while protecting academic integrity and public value. The governance model should be built around three complementary layers:

(1) Strategic steering. The Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation is positioned as a key connector of the university R&I ecosystem, linking internal capacities (faculties, institutes, labs, TTOs, incubators/accelerators) with government, industry, investors and society, and converting national priorities into implementable pathways.

(2) Ecosystem accountability. A Quadruple-helix Advisory Board composed of the university, business sector, public institutions and civil society should co-define priorities, propose thematic challenges and review progress through regular meetings and recommendations.

(3) Operational governance. To reduce fragmentation and bureaucracy, operations should be managed as a portfolio (PMO logic) and supported through clear “playbooks” for technology transfer and IP—disclosure → screening → protection → licensing/spin-off—backed by templates and set decision deadlines.

3.2. National R&I Strategy Alignment

The Strategy must remain tightly aligned with the **Smart Specialisation Strategy 2024–2027**, national innovation instruments, and EU integration pathways. This alignment is an implementation enabler because it: Creates a **clear investment logic** (priority domains, infrastructure upgrades, human capital pipelines, technology transfer frameworks); Improves access to **EU programmes and Widening instruments** (e.g., Horizon Europe, COST, EUREKA) and strengthens international networks and mobility; and Enables “blended finance” pathways by linking university projects to national instruments and reforms (e.g., the transition from FITD functions to the new INOVA agency; and SME-oriented instruments such as credit guarantees, venture/hybrid funds, and green finance).

3.3. Universities

Universities are the primary national performers of research and therefore the key delivery platform for this Strategy. The university-level enablers focus on *institutional capacity*, not only individual excellence: **Professionalized project support (“grant-to-impact”)**. A strengthened project support function is essential for increasing participation and success in Horizon Europe and similar programmes; **Open and service-oriented research infrastructure**. Upgrading labs and equipment and organizing them as shared services (catalogue of services, clear access rules, service-level agreements)

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makes infrastructure usable for SMEs and partners and accelerates validation and prototyping; **Functional technology transfer interface.** The Strategy's "one-stop-shop" logic—support for collaboration, contract research, IP procedures, licensing, and spin-off formation—reduces barriers and increases conversion from research to impact; **Human capital pipelines (PhDs/Industrial PhDs/PostDocs) linked to S3 needs.** Joint supervision with industry and modules on innovation/entrepreneurship/project management increase employability and strengthen academia–industry linkages.

3.4. Cultural Change

In widening contexts, "culture" is often the hidden constraint that prevents good initiatives from scaling. Implementation therefore requires intentional cultural change, anchored in incentives and routines: **CoARA-based incentives** that treat prototypes, patents, licenses, data/software outputs, mentoring, and societal engagement as legitimate outcomes—reducing the "publication-only" logic and making valorisation a normal academic behaviour; **Institutionalised peer learning and capacity building** across faculties (proposal writing, project control, IP, R&I operations), so know-how spreads beyond a few individuals and becomes a shared capability; **Ethics-by-design and responsibility** embedded as default criteria in the innovation pipeline (inclusion, eco-friendly practice, legitimacy with communities).

3.5. International Orientation

International orientation is a practical enabler—bringing partnerships, funding, benchmarks, and talent circulation that compensate for limited domestic resources. Key mechanisms include: **Systemic support for Horizon Europe/COST/EUREKA participation** and structured partnership building at institutional and researcher levels; Leveraging concrete ecosystem assets such as the **EIT Community RIS Hub at UKIM's Business Accelerator** to connect with Europe's innovation networks and catalyse knowledge transfer; **Diaspora and alumni bridges** for mentoring, market access, and investor networks, linked to the idea-to-growth entrepreneurial pathway.

3.6. Stakeholders Communication

Strategic communication should therefore: Use the **Advisory Board** as a permanent feedback loop and legitimacy mechanism; Translate strategy into **clear "front door" entry points** (TTO services, IP clinics, model contracts, innovation vouchers/collaborative calls) that external stakeholders can easily use; Publish an **annual public report on achievements and impact**, based on transparent KPIs (projects, PoCs/prototypes, start-ups/spin-offs), strengthening accountability and stakeholder confidence.

3.7. Digital Transformation

Digital transformation is both a strategic priority and a delivery method. The implementation framework should include: Digitised workflows for **project pipeline management**, partner onboarding, and portfolio oversight (PMO approach), reducing administrative burden and enabling quality assurance and learning loops; Digital enablement of **open science and CoARA evidence**

(narrative CVs, repositories for data/software, dashboards for KPIs and outcomes); Support for S3-aligned digital innovation domains (e.g., ICT, Industry 4.0), while ensuring the Centre functions as the operational node that turns priorities into implementable projects and services.

3.8. Green Transformation

Green transformation must be embedded across research priorities, commercialization pathways, and stakeholder engagement, especially given the region's commitment to decarbonisation and the need for innovation in energy efficiency, sustainable materials, and circular solutions. Implementation should: Prioritize applied R&D and pilot demonstrations in sustainability-relevant areas and maintain demand-oriented portfolios updated through thematic challenges co-defined with external partners; Strengthen green finance and other instruments that support proof-of-concept and scale-up pathways, linked to national SME policy instruments; Treat sustainability, responsibility, and ethics as performance dimensions in R&I, reinforcing legitimacy and long-term impact.

4. Roles and Responsibilities

Effective delivery of this Action Plan depends on clear role definition across the **quadruple-helix** (university–industry–government–society), with the University Entrepreneurship and Innovation Centre (UEIC) acting as the *operational connector* that turns priorities into implementable programmes and measurable results. The stakeholder mapping below assigns responsibilities along the full “research-to-impact” pathway—research excellence, technology transfer, entrepreneurship, ecosystem networking, and CoARA-aligned assessment and impact reporting.

Core implementation roles (University ecosystem)

UEIC (Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation) – Ecosystem Orchestrator (Lead)

- Leads overall coordination of the Action Plan portfolio, ensuring alignment between pillars and sequencing across phases (foundation → expansion → maturation).
- Provides the “front door” for ecosystem users via structured service offers, including: grant-to-impact support, labs-as-a-service access pathways, entrepreneurship pipeline operations, and stakeholder engagement processes.
- Coordinates monitoring and maintains the KPI dashboard, consolidating quantitative indicators and qualitative evidence (impact/innovation/collaboration cases) for annual reporting.
- Ensures permanent connectivity with national and international partners through formal protocols and programme participation.

Technology Transfer Office (UEIC–TTO) – Commercialisation Interface (Lead)

- Operates as a “one-stop shop” for companies, researchers, and investors for contract research, IP procedures, licensing, and spin-off formation.
- Runs IP clinics and deploys model contracts and templates (e.g., NDA, MTA, licensing/option agreements), as well as clear rules for revenue sharing and equity participation.
- Implements a streamlined “valorisation path” (disclosure → novelty/FTO screening → market screening → IP decision → licence/spin-off).
- Works with external patent/legal experts and university legal/finance offices to reduce time-to-decision and transaction costs.

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University Leadership (Rectorate/Senate/Deans) – Strategic Steering and Institutional Adoption (Co-lead)

- Formally adopts the Action Plan, mandates UEIC coordination authority, and ensures institutional-level integration (faculties, institutes, labs, doctoral schools).
- Approves internal policies for CoARA-aligned assessment, open science, and recognition of diverse R&I contributions (not only publications).
- Allocates core funding and incentives that enable sustained delivery (staff roles, seed support, infrastructure access rules).

Faculties, Research Institutes, Labs & Research Groups – Delivery Engines (Lead/Co-lead per programme)

- Produce research outputs and applied solutions aligned with S3 priorities; participate in lighthouse programmes, pilots, and collaborative R&D projects.
- Provide lab services under a “shared access / labs-as-a-service” model and contribute to PoC/prototyping activities and validation with partners.
- Prepare proposal pipelines and participate in Horizon Europe/COST/EUREKA projects supported by UEIC’s grant-to-impact services.

Project Support / Research Office (Grant Support Function) – Fundraising and Compliance (Co-lead)

- Supports proposal development, budgeting, partner-building, compliance and project management, increasing participation and success in international programmes.
- Works closely with UEIC and faculties to maintain continuity from funding capture to outputs and impact evidence.

Institutional Research / Quality Office – Responsible Metrics and Methodological Consistency (Co-lead)

- Ensures KPI definitions, data quality, and harmonisation with national and EU indicator frameworks, reducing reporting burden and enabling benchmarking.
- Supports implementation of CoARA-aligned qualitative assessment and discipline-sensitive rubrics, tracking uptake over time.

Library, IT Units, Ethics/Integrity Bodies – Open Science and Responsible Research Infrastructure (Support/Co-lead)

- Enables open access publishing, DMP workflows, repositories, and responsible data/security practices.
- Ensures ethics, integrity and governance checks are embedded into project workflows and evidence bases for assessment and annual reporting.

Ecosystem governance and accountability roles

Quadruple-Helix Advisory Board (University–Business–Public Institutions–Civil Society) – Ecosystem Accountability (Co-lead)

- Co-defines thematic priorities and challenge briefs, validates relevance of UEIC services, and monitors progress through regular meetings and recommendations.
- Reviews annual KPI/impact reporting and recommends course corrections, including portfolio reprioritisation based on evidence and stakeholder feedback.
- Serves as a legitimacy mechanism for public value delivery (economic, societal and environmental outcomes), and supports scaling partnerships.

External stakeholder roles (national, regional, international)

Government bodies & policymakers (Ministries, line ministries, agencies) – Policy alignment, instruments, and demand-side pull (Co-lead)

- Provide stable policy direction and align funding instruments with Action Plan pillars (HR pipelines, infrastructure, TT/IP, entrepreneurship, green/digital transformation).
- Mobilise demand-side innovation tools: pilot procurement, regulatory sandboxes (where relevant), and challenge-driven calls that create real adoption pathways for validated solutions.
- Participate in formal partnerships/protocols with UEIC and the university to implement joint projects, pilots and contract research.

National innovation/funding structures (e.g., innovation funding instruments) – Financing pathways and co-investment (Co-lead)

- Co-design and co-finance instruments such as innovation vouchers, collaborative grants, PoC support, and programmes enabling industrial PhDs and joint R&D.
- Provide predictable routes from proof-of-concept to scale by coordinating grant and investment readiness components with UEIC's pipeline services.

Municipalities and regional bodies – Local testbeds and implementation partners (Co-lead/Support)

- Offer local problem sets and living-lab environments for pilots (digital/green services, mobility, energy, circular economy), and facilitate adoption in public services.
- Co-host innovation calls and provide co-funding or in-kind support (access, data, infrastructure, regulatory facilitation) via operational protocols.

Industry and SMEs (companies, clusters, chambers) – Co-creation, adoption, and demand articulation (Co-lead)

- Co-define research problems, provide validation environments, co-fund contract research, and adopt/licence solutions where appropriate.
- Engage through chambers/clusters and contribute to structured instruments (innovation vouchers, collaborative calls, industrial PhDs).
- Provide external validation evidence (pilot adoption documents, testimonials, satisfaction feedback) used in UEIC impact reporting.

Start-ups and university spin-offs – Commercialisation vehicles (Lead for venture execution)

- Participate in the staged entrepreneurial pipeline (ideation → incubation → acceleration → scaling), and generate evidence of market traction and learning.
- Work with UEIC-TTO to licence IP or structure IP-to-equity models (where relevant), and to meet governance and compliance standards for investment readiness.

Incubators/accelerators and ecosystem intermediaries – Capacity scaling and specialised support (Support/Co-lead)

- Provide programme delivery capacity (mentors, curricula, cohort management), specialised acceleration services, and market-entry networks.
- Partner with UEIC to avoid fragmentation and ensure consistent quality standards and progression logic across pipeline stages.

Investors (angels, VC, impact funds), banks, and IFIs – Capital + discipline + networks (Co-lead)

- Participate in investment-readiness programmes, provide feedback on deal quality, and co-create funding pathways (pre-seed/seed, convertible instruments, co-investment).
- Offer non-financial value: governance coaching, market access, and international scaling networks.

Civil society organisations and communities – Societal demand and validation (Co-lead/Support)

- Contribute challenge definitions, inclusion priorities, and real-world validation contexts, particularly for mission-oriented R&I and social innovation.

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- Support transparent impact narratives and legitimacy of outcomes (social value, environmental impact, public trust).

International networks and EU programmes (Horizon Europe, COST, EUREKA, EIT communities) – Internationalisation and integration channels (Co-lead)

- Provide consortia opportunities, best practices, mobility, and market-oriented project pipelines.
- UEIC coordinates participation and partner-building, leveraging EIT communities and accelerator networks to access expertise, partnerships and funding.

Practical responsibility logic (how roles connect to action delivery)

To reduce fragmentation, responsibilities are organised around: (1) **delivery ownership** (UEIC + faculties/labs + TTO), (2) **ecosystem accountability** (Advisory Board), and (3) **shared monitoring and learning** (UEIC dashboard + institutional quality office + stakeholder validation).

This ensures that each programme has a clear lead, that partnerships move beyond MoUs into operational protocols and joint projects, and that impact is demonstrated through both indicators and verified external evidence—including adoption documents, partner surveys and documented flagship cases.

5. Timeline and Milestones

The implementation of this Research and Innovation Action Plan is structured around a clear sequence of milestones that support the gradual maturation of the Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation and the wider national R&I ecosystem. The milestones are organised into coherent phases that reflect the logical progression from institutional setup to ecosystem expansion, and ultimately to demonstrable impact and consolidation. This phased approach ensures that foundational capacities, such as governance structures, technology transfer mechanisms, research infrastructure, and evaluation reforms, are firmly established before large-scale collaborative programmes and entrepreneurial pipelines are fully deployed.

Each phase is purposefully designed to reinforce the previous one. The first phase lays the institutional and policy groundwork by establishing advisory structures, strengthening research capabilities and adopting CoARA-aligned assessment practices. The second phase focuses on operationalising these structures through the rollout of shared research services, industry-academia instruments, lighthouse programmes, and internationalisation activities. The final phase emphasises measurable outcomes, system-level monitoring, and the integration of impact evidence into institutional decision-making. Collectively, these phases provide a roadmap that is ambitious yet realistic, allowing the ecosystem to scale sustainably, track progress transparently, and position itself as a competitive and impactful contributor to national and European research and innovation priorities.

Phase 1 - Foundation and institutional set-up (Q1 2026 – Q2 2027).

The first phase focuses on establishing the institutional foundations necessary for a modern research and innovation ecosystem. The Advisory Board with quadruple-helix representation is formed early, ensuring legitimacy and ecosystem alignment. A central milestone is the launch of the Technology Transfer Office, which becomes the single point of contact for intellectual property, contract research, material transfer agreements, and industry collaboration. In parallel, the university begins upgrading priority research laboratories into shared “labs-as-a-service,” enabling external access for SMEs, start-ups and researchers. Strategic frameworks are adopted in this phase: CoARA-compliant evaluation reforms, Open Science integration, and narrative CV structures. A set of doctoral,

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industrial PhD and postdoctoral programmes are initiated to prepare a new generation of researchers in S3 domains. These structural and policy milestones lay the groundwork for efficient project execution, improved research culture and stronger alignment with European standards.

Key milestones include:

- Establishment of the Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation Advisory Board and adoption of Terms of Reference
- Creation and staffing of the Technology Transfer Office (TTO) as a one-stop-shop
- Initial implementation of CoARA-aligned assessment policies and narrative CV templates
- Early upgrades of research laboratories and digital infrastructure
- Development of doctoral and postdoctoral programmes aligned with S3 priorities
- Signing of key national and international cooperation agreements (MoUs, protocols)
- Approval of Open Science and research integrity guidelines

Phase 2 - Expansion, implementation and ecosystem integration (Q3 2027 – Q4 2027).

This phase emphasises expansion from planning into full-scale implementation. By mid-2027, research laboratories are fully functional as shared infrastructure platforms, enabling companies and public bodies to access testing, prototyping and measurement services. Funding instruments for academia–industry cooperation are launched, stimulating collaborative research and increasing industry participation. The entrepreneurial pathway becomes operational: pre-incubation, incubation, acceleration and scale-up activities are integrated into a coherent system supported by mentors, alumni and diaspora. Lighthouse programmes are activated to pilot green and digital transformation initiatives that directly address national S3 priorities. Investment ecosystems mature through consistent engagement with investors, banks, domestic and international financial institutions. EU-funded project participation accelerates during this phase, supported by strengthened project offices and international partnerships. CoARA reforms deepen as faculties adopt discipline-sensitive assessment models and integrate open science practices into everyday research workflows.

Some of the key milestones are:

- Full operationalisation of research infrastructure services (labs-as-a-service)
- Rollout of innovation vouchers, collaborative research grants and industrial PhD schemes
- Launch of lighthouse programmes for green and digital transformation
- Introduction of mentoring systems, entrepreneurial pipelines, and SME Academy modules
- Activation of investment-readiness programmes and partnerships with banks, angels, VC funds and international financial institutions
- Expansion of internationalisation activities (Horizon Europe, COST, EUREKA, EIT KIC collaborations)
- Deployment of CoARA assessment rubrics and discipline-specific guidelines across faculties.

Phase 3 — Maturation, impact and systemic consolidation (Q1 2028 – Q4 2028).

The final phase marks a shift from building structures to demonstrating measurable impact. The KPI dashboard becomes fully operational, enabling transparent monitoring of R&I activities and informing decision-making. The annual Impact Report, aligned with CoARA principles, documents scientific, societal and economic contributions, supported by externally validated cases from industry and the public sector. Entrepreneurship support programmes yield concrete outputs such as new start-ups, licensing deals and increased SME competitiveness. Internationalisation reaches maturity with higher Horizon Europe success rates, increased mobility, and robust partnerships with EU universities, research and technology organizations, and research infrastructures. Institutional practices for Open Science, responsible research evaluation and stakeholder engagement become

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firmly embedded. Through this consolidation, the university positions itself as a national and regional leader in research-driven economic development and innovation.

The phase's key milestones are:

- Full deployment of the Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation KPI dashboard and annual Impact Report
- Demonstrable increase in Horizon Europe participation and international co-publications
- Documented set of flagship impact, innovation and collaboration cases validated by external stakeholders
- Growth in spin-outs, licensing agreements and industrial research projects
- Measurable outcomes from SME Academy participation and entrepreneurial pipeline progression
- Completion of EU-level integration activities and recognition of institutional CoARA compliance
- Ecosystem satisfaction surveys and external validation mechanisms institutionalised.

Considering this, Table 5 presents an overview of the pillars, programmes or actions in each pillar, the engaged ecosystem actors, indicated time period, and KPIs for tracking the progress.

Table 5: Overview of timeline and activities

Pillar	Programme / Action	Engaged ecosystem actors	Start date (quarter)	End date (quarter)	KPIs
1. Research Excellence and Alignment with Smart Specialisation Areas	1.1 Development of human resources for research and development (PhDs, Industrial PhDs, post-doctoral candidates)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation; • Doctoral schools; • Faculties and research institutes; • Companies and public sector organisations in smart specialization domains; • Ministry of Education and Science; • INOVA/innovation fund 	Q1 2026	Q4 2028	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # of new PhD or industrial PhD or post-doc positions in smart specialization areas; • % of PhD or industrial PhD projects with joint academic-industry supervision; • # of doctoral modules on innovation, entrepreneurship, project management delivered per year
	1.2 Modernisation of research infrastructure and open access (labs-as-a-service)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation; • University management; • Faculties and laboratories; • IT and research infrastructure units; 	Q2 2026	Q4 2027	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # of laboratories or e-infrastructure units upgraded; • # of external users (SMEs/start-ups/industry) accessing shared services annually; • % of service requests delivered within agreed Service Level Agreement

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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SMEs, start-ups and large companies as users; • Relevant ministries/INOVA 			
	1.3 Applied research for green and digital transformation (lighthouse programmes)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation; • Smart specialization research teams; • Companies and SME coalitions; • Municipalities • Line ministries (energy, environment, digitalisation); • Civil society 	Q3 2026	Q4 2028	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # of lighthouse research programmes launched in smart specialization priority domains; • # of applied R&D projects and pilot demonstrations with external partners per year; • # of prototypes or proofs of concept or demonstrators delivered
	1.4 Internationalisation of research and integration into European networks (Horizon, COST, EUREKA, infrastructures)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation; • Faculties and institutes; • National contact points; • International university and industry partners; • European research infrastructures 	Q2 2026	Q4 2028	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # of Horizon Europe or COST or EUREKA proposals submitted • # of funded Horizon Europe or COST or EUREKA proposals; • # of international co-authored publications or joint projects; • # of incoming and outgoing research mobilities
	1.5 CoARA-compliant tools for assessing and stimulating research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation; 	Q1 2026	Q2 2027	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CoARA-aligned assessment guidelines adopted (yes/no) and % of evaluation procedures using narrative CV;

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	(narrative CV, recognition of open science and valorisation)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • University leadership; • HR and promotion committees; • Research office; • Ethics and integrity boards 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # of cases where open science or valorisation outputs (data, software, impact) are explicitly recognised in assessments
2. Technology Transfer (TT), Intellectual Property (IP) and Knowledge Valorization	2.1 Establishment of a Technology Transfer Office as “one-stop-shop”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation or Technology Transfer Office; • Faculties and research groups; • Legal and finance offices; • Companies, start-ups, investors; • Chambers of commerce and clusters of companies 	Q1 2026	Q4 2026	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology Transfer Office formally established and staffed (yes/no; # of full-time equivalents); • # of invention disclosures per year; • # of IP or TT consultations and clinics delivered; • # of licenses, options and spin-offs created
	2.2 Simplifying intellectual property management (templates, faster procedures, clear paths to market)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation or Technology Transfer Office; • University legal office; • External patent attorneys; 	Q2 2026	Q2 2027	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Average time from disclosure to IP decision; • # of standardised IP templates adopted (non-disclosure agreements, material transfer agreements, license, revenue-sharing); • Average user satisfaction score on IP services

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers and project principal investigators 			
	2.3 Instruments for encouraging academia–industry cooperation (innovation vouchers, collaborative grants, industrial PhDs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation; • INOVA or innovation fund and other funding bodies; • Companies and SMEs; • Chambers and business associations; • Ministries 	Q3 2026	Q4 2028	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # and total value of innovation vouchers or collaborative grants awarded; • # of industrial PhD agreements signed; • # of contract research projects with companies per year
3. Development of Highly Innovative Entrepreneurship	3.1 Entrepreneurial path from idea to growth (structured pipeline: idea → pre-incubation → incubation → acceleration → scale-up)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation and incubator or accelerator; • Faculties; • Student and researcher teams; • Start-ups and spin-offs; • Regional accelerators; • EIT Knowledge and Innovation Communities (KICs) 	Q2 2026	Q4 2028	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End-to-end entrepreneurial pathway formally adopted (yes/no); • # of teams in each stage of the pipeline per cohort; • # of demo days or pitch events organised per year; • Progression rate of teams between stages
	3.2 Mentoring system and programmes with alumni and diaspora	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation; • Alumni & diaspora networks; 	Q3 2026	Q4 2028	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # of active mentors (local and diaspora); • # of mentoring sessions or hours delivered per year; • # of teams matched with mentors; • Average satisfaction rating of mentoring

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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Entrepreneurs and industry experts; • Investors and business angels; • Student and researcher teams 			
	3.3 Investment readiness and connection to financial instruments (banks, angels, VC, IFIs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation; • Local and international banks; • Business angel networks; • Venture capital funds and international financial institutions; • INOVA or innovation instruments; • Start-ups and spin-offs 	Q3 2026	Q4 2028	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # of teams completing investment-readiness programme; • # of investor meetings and pitch events facilitated; • # of teams obtaining pre-seed or seed funding; • Total external capital raised by supported teams
	3.4 SME Academy (executive education, micro-credentials, applied clinics)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation; • Faculties; • Chambers of commerce; • Sectoral associations; • SMEs and scale-ups 	Q1 2027	Q4 2028	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # of micro-credential modules developed and delivered; • # of SME participants trained; • % of SMEs reporting implemented improvements 6–12 months after training
4. Ecosystem Networking and Internationalisation	4.1 Advisory Board with quadruple helix system (university–business–public sector–civil society)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation; 	Q1 2026	Q2 2026 (establ	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advisory Board formally established with adopted Terms of Reference (yes/no);

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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • University leadership; • Representatives of business sector, ministries and agencies, municipalities and civil society 		ishment)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # of meetings held per year; • # of formal recommendations issued; • % of priority recommendations implemented or in progress
	4.2 Formal partnerships with key institutions and intermediaries (Memorandums of Understanding, protocols)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation; • Ministries and agencies for innovation, economy, education; • Municipalities and regional bodies; • Chambers of commerce; • Industrial clusters; • Science and tech parks 	Q2 2026	Q4 2027	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # of signed Memorandums of Understanding or operational cooperation protocols; • # of joint projects, pilots or contract-research initiatives launched; • # of students and SMEs engaged through these partnerships
	4.3 EU integration through European programmes (Horizon, EIT, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation; • Faculties and institutes; • National Horizon contact structure; • European universities, research and technology organizations, companies; • EIT Regional Innovation Scheme (RIS) Hub 	Q3 2026	Q4 2028	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # of Horizon Europe or EIT or COST or EUREKA consortia with the participation of the Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation participation; • Total value of EU-funded R&I projects acquired; • # of staff trained in EU project development and management; • Success rate of submitted proposals (%)

<p>5. CoARA Reform & Impact Measurement</p>	<p>5.1 CoARA assessment policy and discipline-sensitive rubrics</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation; • University senate; • HR and promotion committees; • Quality assurance office; • Faculties 	<p>Q1 2026</p>	<p>Q1 2027</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CoARA-compliant assessment policy adopted (yes/no, year); • # of disciplines with tailored rubrics; • % of promotion or recruitment decisions using CoARA rubrics instead of traditional criteria
	<p>5.2 Narrative evidence (Impact, Innovation, Collaboration Cases)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers and project leaders; • Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation; • Research office 	<p>Q2 2026</p>	<p>Q4 2027</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standard templates for narrative cases approved and in use (yes/no); • # of Impact or Innovation or Collaboration Cases submitted annually; • % of major funding or promotion decisions that explicitly reference narrative evidence
	<p>5.3 Balanced CoARA KPI set and scorecard</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation; • Institutional research office; • Data and IT team; • Advisory Board 	<p>Q2 2026</p>	<p>Q2 2027</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation scorecard approved (yes/no); • # of KPIs tracked across capacity, process quality, outputs and outcomes; • Frequency of KPI updates (reports/year); • # of internal users accessing KPI dashboards
	<p>5.4 Open Science & integrity integration (DMPs, OA, ethics)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation; • University library; • IT services; 	<p>Q3 2026</p>	<p>Q4 2028</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • % of funded projects with approved Data Management Plans and ethics checks; • % of publications in open access;

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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ethics and integrity committees; • Researchers 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # of datasets or software outputs shared (where feasible); • # of staff trained in open science and research integrity
	5.5 Stakeholder-validated impact (partner letters, pilots, surveys)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation; • Advisory Board; • Companies and public sector partners; • NGOs and civil society; • Investors 	Q3 2026	Q4 2028	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # of external validation letters or pilot adoption documents collected per year; • Annual partner satisfaction survey conducted (yes/no); • Survey response rate and average satisfaction score; • # of flagship impact cases documented with external evidence
	5.6 Incentives, digital dashboard and annual UEIC Impact Report	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation; • HR and finance units; • IT and data team; • Communications office; • Other external stakeholders (for dissemination) 	Q1 2027	Q4 2028	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital R&I or impact dashboard operational (yes/no); • # of active users; • # of staff receiving mini-grants recognition for mentoring, TT or engagement; • Annual Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation Impact Report produced and published (yes/no); • # of downloads or views or dissemination events of the report

The process for achieving the milestones and active contribution towards each is also presented visually in a Gantt chart (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Gantt chart of key programmes and activities

6. Monitoring and Evaluation

Effective implementation of this Action Plan requires a robust monitoring and evaluation (M&E) system that tracks progress, supports learning and enables evidence-based decisions. The monitoring framework is built around a logic from capacity to processes to outputs to outcomes and impact, in line with international practice for research and innovation policy evaluation (OECD, 2016). It combines quantitative KPIs with qualitative evidence, such as impact/innovation/collaboration cases, narrative CVs and partner testimonials to avoid a narrow focus on publication counts and to reflect CoARA principles of responsible research assessment. The proposed KPIs can be segmented into several categories based on the rationale, purpose and data availability. This typology is described as follows.

Capacity and input indicators

These KPIs capture the resources and capabilities that underpin the ecosystem: number of PhD, Industrial PhD and PostDoc positions in S3 domains; FTEs in the TTO and UEIC; number of upgraded laboratories and digital infrastructures; staff trained in open science, research integrity and EU project development. Such indicators reflect the so-called enabling conditions for research and innovation and are standard in OECD and EU frameworks for STI monitoring, which emphasise tracking investment in human capital, infrastructures and organisational capabilities (OECD, 2024).

Process and quality indicators

Process KPIs measure how services are delivered rather than only what they produce. Examples include the number of IP/TT consultations, average time from disclosure to IP decision, share of lab service requests delivered within agreed SLAs, number of advisory board meetings held, and use of CoARA-aligned rubrics in assessment procedures. These indicators are important because they monitor whether new governance arrangements, TTO services, labs-as-a-service and advisory structures are functioning efficiently and transparently. International guidance on innovation policy evaluation stresses the need to link indicators to the intervention logic and to track the quality of implementation, not only final outcomes (Taftie, 2015).

Output indicators

Output KPIs capture the immediate, measurable results of activities: number of collaborative R&D projects and lighthouse programmes launched; innovation vouchers and collaborative grants awarded; invention disclosures, licenses and spin-offs; Horizon Europe and other EU proposals submitted and funded; number of entrepreneurs, SMEs and students supported in the entrepreneurial pathway and SME Academy. Research on incubators and innovation ecosystems highlights that such indicators like number of start-ups supported, services provided, collaborations established are central to assessing whether support structures are active and relevant for their users (Azadnia et al., 2022).

Outcome and impact indicators

At a higher level, the Action Plan uses outcome KPIs such as: capital raised by supported teams; number of SMEs reporting concrete improvements like new markets, digitalisation, green practices, following support; growth in international co-publications and EU project funding; evidence of adoption of UEIC solutions in companies and public bodies; partner satisfaction scores; and externally validated impact cases. This is consistent with the European Commission's "Key Impact Pathways" approach for Horizon Europe, which encourages monitoring knowledge creation, societal value and economic impact over time rather than only scientific outputs (European Commission, 2023). In the entrepreneurship and incubation literature, there is growing emphasis on moving beyond survival

counts toward indicators of learning, network formation, resource acquisition and long-term performance of supported firms, which this Action Plan reflects (Pattanasak et al., 2022).

Responsible research assessment and culture change

Several KPIs are explicitly linked to CoARA and open-science reforms: percentage of evaluation procedures using narrative CVs, recognition of a wider range of contributions, including open data, software, mentoring, stakeholder engagement, as well as, share of publications in open access, and the number of Impact/Innovation/Collaboration Cases used in major decisions. Evidence from Science Europe and recent RRA case-studies shows that narrative CVs and broader assessment criteria can shift attention from journal metrics to diverse forms of impact, provided that their uptake is monitored and supported with training (Tzouganatou, 2025).

Monitoring will follow a tiered time schedule, aligned with both operational needs and strategic decision cycles:

- **Quarterly monitoring for operational and process KPIs:** use of labs-as-a-service, number of service requests and SLA performance, participation in mentoring sessions and entrepreneurial activities, uptake of TTO services, number of events, and internal training activities. Quarterly tracking allows the UEIC team to detect bottlenecks early (e.g. capacity constraints in labs or TTO) and adjust procedures, as recommended in good practice guides on continuous performance monitoring for innovation support organisations.
- **Annual monitoring for strategic outputs and outcomes:** number and value of collaborative R&D projects and innovation vouchers, EU project success rates, IP and spin-off portfolio, start-up and SME performance indicators, uptake of CoARA-aligned assessment, and implementation of open-science practices. Annual reviews will be synthesised in the UEIC Impact Report and shared with the Advisory Board and university leadership to inform budget allocations and strategic priorities, reflecting international practice in R&I programme evaluation.
- **Mid-term and final evaluations for long-term impact:** at mid-term (around 2027) and at the end of the period (2028), the KPI time series will be complemented by qualitative methods (case studies, interviews, focus groups with ecosystem partners) to assess systemic changes in the regional innovation ecosystem and contribution to national S3 priorities. OECD work on mission-oriented policies and innovation ecosystems emphasises the importance of combining indicators with theory-based evaluation and stakeholder reflection to understand complex, long-term impacts.

Responsibility for monitoring

Responsibility for monitoring is shared. Moreover, the UEIC coordinates data collection and maintains the KPI dashboard; the institutional research/quality office ensures methodological consistency and alignment with national and European indicator frameworks; and the Advisory Board periodically reviews results and recommends adjustments. Wherever possible, indicators are harmonised with existing national and EU reporting, such as Horizon Europe, EIT, innovation fund instruments, and similar, to reduce administrative burden and enable benchmarking. A more in-depth outlook of the KPIs, explanations, units, and frequency of measurement is given in Table 6.

Table 6: Overview of proposed KPIs

KPI	Definition	Unit	Frequency
Number of new PhD / Industrial PhD / PostDoc positions in S3 areas	Counts newly created and funded PhD, Industrial PhD and PostDoc positions aligned with S3 priority domains.	Number of positions	Annual
% of PhD / Industrial PhD projects with joint	Share of doctoral projects that have both academic and	Percentage (%)	Annual

academic–industry supervision	industry/public-sector supervisors formally appointed.		
Number of doctoral modules on innovation / entrepreneurship / project management	Measures extent to which transversal skills are integrated into doctoral training.	Number of modules delivered per year	Annual
Number of laboratories / e-infrastructure units upgraded	Counts labs and e-infrastructure units that reach agreed modernisation standards (equipment, software, QA).	Number of labs/units	Annual
Number of external users accessing shared services	Counts distinct external organisations (SMEs, start-ups, large firms, public bodies) using labs-as-a-service or e-services.	Number of external organisations	Quarterly; Annual
% of service requests delivered within agreed SLA	Share of service requests completed within the time and quality parameters set in the Service Level Agreement.	Percentage (%)	Quarterly
Number of invention disclosures per year	Counts new invention, software or know-how disclosure forms submitted to the TTO.	Number of disclosures	Annual
Number of IP / TT consultations and clinics delivered	Measures the volume of support provided by TTO (1:1 consultations, clinics, workshops).	Number of consultations / sessions	Quarterly; Annual
Average time from disclosure to IP decision	Average duration between formal invention disclosure and IP decision (file / not file / other route).	Average days or weeks	Annual
Number of standardised IP templates adopted	Counts standardised legal templates in official use (e.g. NDA, MTA, licence, revenue-sharing).	Number of templates	Annual
Number of licences, options and spin-offs created	Measures commercialisation outcomes via licence/option agreements and formal spin-off registrations.	Number of deals / spin-offs	Annual
Number and total value of innovation vouchers / collaborative grants awarded	Captures volume of funded academia–industry collaborative projects.	Count and total EUR value	Annual
Number of industrial PhD agreements signed	Counts formal agreements for industrial PhDs involving companies/public bodies.	Number of agreements	Annual
Number of contract research projects with companies	Measures commissioned research projects funded by companies or associations.	Number of projects	Annual
Number of teams in each stage of the entrepreneurial pipeline	Shows how many teams are at idea, pre-incubation,	Number of teams per stage	Per cohort; Annual

	incubation, acceleration and scale-up stages.		
Progression rate of teams between stages	Share of teams that advance from one pipeline stage to the next within a defined period.	Percentage (%)	Per cohort; Annual
Number of demo days / pitch events organised	Measures intensity of exposure activities towards investors and partners.	Number of events per year	Annual
Number of teams completing investment-readiness programmes	Counts teams that complete structured investment-readiness training (curriculum fully completed).	Number of teams	Annual
Number of investor meetings and pitch events facilitated	Measures connections created with investors (angels, VC, banks, IFIs).	Number of meetings / events	Annual
Number of teams obtaining pre-seed / seed funding and total capital raised	Captures financial success of supported ventures.	Count of funded teams; total EUR raised	Annual
Number of micro-credential modules developed and delivered (SME Academy)	Measures breadth of SME training offer (e.g. digital, export, green skills).	Number of modules per year	Annual
Number of SME participants trained	Counts SME representatives who participate in training activities.	Number of participants	Annual
% of SMEs reporting implemented improvements 6–12 months after training	Share of SME participants that report concrete changes (e.g. new markets, tools, processes).	Percentage (%)	6–12 months after each cohort; Annual synthesis
Advisory Board formally established and ToR adopted	Confirms establishment of the quadruple-helix Advisory Board with approved Terms of Reference.	Yes/No; date	One-off; annual status check
Number of Advisory Board meetings and formal recommendations	Measures level of activity and guidance provided by the Board.	Number of meetings; number of recommendations	Annual
% of priority recommendations implemented or in progress	Share of Board's priority recommendations that have led to concrete action.	Percentage (%)	Annual
Number of signed MoUs / cooperation protocols with key actors	Counts formal cooperation agreements with ministries, agencies, clusters, chambers, RTOs, universities, etc.	Number of MoUs/protocols	Annual
Number of joint projects, pilots or contract-research initiatives under MoUs	Measures whether MoUs translate into concrete collaborative activities.	Number of projects/pilots	Annual
Number of Horizon Europe / EIT / COST / EUREKA	Captures international fundraising effort and success.	Count of proposals; count	Quarterly (internal);

proposals submitted and funded; total EU R&I funding		funded; total EUR	Annual (official)
Number of international co-authored publications and mobilities	Measures scientific integration and researcher mobility with international partners.	Number of publications; number of mobilities	Annual
CoARA-compliant assessment policy adopted	Indicates formal adoption of CoARA-aligned research assessment at institutional level.	Yes/No; adoption year	One-off; status review every 2–3 years
% of promotion / recruitment procedures using narrative CVs and CoARA rubrics	Shows extent of implementation of new assessment practices.	Percentage (%)	Annual
Number of Impact / Innovation / Collaboration Narrative Cases submitted	Counts use of narrative evidence in evaluations and reporting.	Number of cases per year	Annual
% of publications in Open Access	Measures adoption of Open Science publishing practices.	Percentage (%)	Annual
Number of datasets / software outputs shared	Captures sharing of research data and software where feasible.	Number of datasets/software items	Annual
Number of staff trained in Open Science and research integrity	Measures capacity building in responsible research practices.	Number of staff trained	Annual
Number of external validation letters / pilot adoption documents	Counts formal external confirmations of use/adoption of UEIC outputs (letters, MOUs, official notes).	Number of documents per year	Annual
Partner satisfaction survey conducted; response rate; average satisfaction score	Tracks ecosystem perception of UEIC services and collaborations.	Yes/No (survey); response %; average score (e.g. 1–5)	Annual
Number of flagship impact cases documented with external evidence	Counts high-quality impact case studies backed by data and external validation.	Number of cases per year	Annual
UEIC scorecard approved and digital KPI dashboard operational	Indicates whether the monitoring system is formalised and in active use.	Yes/No; go-live date	One-off; annual status review
Number of internal users accessing KPI dashboards and report frequency	Measures actual use of monitoring information by leadership and staff.	Number of active users; number of reports per year	Quarterly; Annual
Annual UEIC Impact Report produced; views/downloads; dissemination events	Tracks transparency and outreach of impact reporting.	Yes/No (report); number of views/downloads; number of events	Annual

Data collection

Data for these KPIs will be collected primarily from existing institutional systems and administrative records, complemented by targeted surveys and evaluation tools. Human resources and training indicators will rely on HR databases, doctoral school and curriculum records. Technology transfer and IP-related KPIs will be drawn from the TTO's disclosure logs, case management tools and contract archives, while financial and collaboration indicators (e.g. vouchers, grants, contract research) will use project management systems and financial records. Entrepreneurship and SME support KPIs will be monitored through incubator/accelerator CRMs, programme completion lists and follow-up assessments. Governance and internationalisation indicators will be based on formal decisions, MoUs, project office statistics, bibliometric outputs and mobility records. Finally, CoARA, Open Science and impact-related KPIs will combine repository statistics, training participation data, narrative case repositories, external validation letters, and regular stakeholder and partner satisfaction surveys, all aggregated through a central UEIC scorecard and digital KPI dashboard.

The purpose of M&E is not merely to produce reports but to support learning and adaptive management. Regular analysis of KPIs will be used to refine the design of support instruments like innovation vouchers, and training modules, rebalance resources between research, technology transfer and entrepreneurship activities, and identify where additional partnerships or policy reforms are needed. In this sense, when monitoring systems are explicitly linked to decision-making and learning, rather than only accountability, they are more likely to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of R&I interventions (OECD, 2024).

At the same time, the Action Plan recognises the limitations of purely quantitative KPIs. This is why the monitoring system is complemented by narrative impact cases, stakeholder surveys and external validation letters, reflecting emerging best practice in responsible research assessment and impact evaluation.

7. Risk Management

A first group of risks relates to governance clarity and operational speed. If mandates overlap across units, decision-making slows and duplication increases. This is mitigated through formal Terms of Reference, a RACI matrix, time-bound decisions (especially for IP and partnership approvals), and escalation routes from UEIC management to steering structures. Closely linked is the risk of **administrative and procurement delays**, which can block infrastructure upgrades, pilots, and project delivery; mitigation therefore focuses on standardized procedures, model templates, service-level agreements, and digitized workflows that reduce cycle time and improve accountability.

A second group of risks concerns financing and sustainability. In a widening context, funding volatility and under-resourcing can stop good initiatives from scaling. To reduce this risk, the Action Plan relies on a diversified resource model—university baseline capacity plus EU project overheads, service-based lab access (“labs-as-a-service”), contract research, and alignment with national instruments—combined with phased implementation so that “front door” services (project support and TTO/IP functions) remain operational even under budget pressure.

A third group is tied to technology transfer and market uptake. There is a real risk of low adoption of TTO services, weak disclosure pipelines, and limited commercialization outcomes if researchers see IP processes as slow or unrewarding. Mitigation is built around visible, easy-to-use services (IP clinics, templates such as NDA/MTA, faster decisions via a standing IP committee), and incentives that recognize commercialization and engagement as valid outcomes. Similarly, R&I outputs may remain weakly market-oriented if demand-side pull is missing; the Action Plan therefore emphasizes pilots, living labs, proof-of-concept validation with companies/municipalities, and stage-gate decisions that allow pivoting early when the market signal is weak. Regulatory and legal uncertainty for IP licensing and spin-off equity will be handled through clear internal rules (ownership, revenue-sharing, conflict-of-interest safeguards) and external legal/patent support, with interim

commercialization routes (e.g., know-how or software licensing, option agreements) where full protection is not yet optimal.

A fourth group of risks affects ecosystem cooperation and legitimacy. Partnerships may remain symbolic when MoUs are not translated into operational protocols and joint pipelines. This is mitigated by attaching implementation annexes to partnerships (deliverables, timelines, pilots), using annual challenge briefs, and applying Advisory Board follow-up to maintain momentum. Trust and reputation risks—including concerns about transparency or conflicts of interest—are mitigated through documented decisions, integrity checks, stakeholder validation evidence, and annual public reporting.

Finally, implementation risks related to people, digital transformation, and international orientation are managed explicitly. Skills gaps, turnover, and brain drain are addressed through training plans, documented playbooks, clear roles, and short-term expert support if capacity gaps arise. Digital risks (data quality, interoperability, GDPR/cybersecurity) are mitigated through data governance rules and a “minimum viable dashboard” approach that prioritizes reliable indicators over complexity. Internationalization risks—such as limited success in EU programmes—are reduced through proposal pipeline management, peer review, structured partner-building, and incremental participation strategies that build track record.

8. Conclusion and Recommendations

This Action Plan translates the R&I Strategy into an operational, phased roadmap that supports the gradual maturation of the Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation (UEIC) and the wider national R&I ecosystem—moving from institutional set-up, through ecosystem integration, to demonstrable impact and consolidation by 2028. The Plan is designed to reduce fragmentation by clarifying ownership and accountability, ensuring that partnerships move beyond memoranda into working protocols and joint projects, and demonstrating progress through indicators and verified external evidence. A central conclusion is that UEIC must function as the system’s “front door” and operational connector—coordinating the portfolio across phases, delivering structured services (grant-to-impact support, labs-as-a-service access, entrepreneurship pipeline operations, and stakeholder engagement), and maintaining the KPI dashboard and annual reporting package. This coordinating role is reinforced by two cross-cutting priorities that make the whole system work in practice: (1) ecosystem networking and internationalisation, and (2) CoARA-aligned assessment and impact measurement.

Recommendations for successful delivery (institutional and ecosystem level) focus on eight practical commitments:

First, lock in governance and decision speed. Establish and actively use the Quadruple-Helix Advisory Board with clear Terms of Reference and a regular rhythm for setting thematic challenges and monitoring progress, while keeping responsibilities organised around delivery ownership, ecosystem accountability, and shared monitoring/learning.

Second, secure minimum viable, stable capacity for the UEIC operating model (core team, TTO operations, dashboard and reporting), so foundational services remain reliable across funding cycles and can scale as demand grows.

Third, professionalise technology transfer as a “one-stop shop”. Prioritise fast, researcher-friendly processes (IP clinics, templates, standing decisions, clear routes to market) so that contract research, licensing and spin-off formation become routine rather than exceptional outcomes.

Fourth, make research infrastructure usable for the economy by operationalising labs-as-a-service with transparent access rules and service-level agreements, so SMEs, start-ups and public partners can test, prototype and validate solutions.

Fifth, institutionalise the entrepreneurship pipeline (idea → pre-incubation → incubation → acceleration → scaling) and connect it systematically to mentoring, diaspora/alumni networks and investment readiness, ensuring that promising teams can progress stage-by-stage.

Sixth, hardwire EU integration through programmes and networks, not only ad hoc projects—via structured support for Horizon Europe participation and use of EIT communities/accelerator networks for partnerships, expertise and market-oriented project pipelines.

Seventh, implement CoARA reforms as an enabling system, using discipline-sensitive rubrics, narrative evidence formats (Impact/Innovation/Collaboration cases), and a balanced scorecard that tracks capacity → process quality → outputs → outcomes/impact while avoiding narrow metric “decision rules.”

Eighth, close the loop with learning-based monitoring and transparency. Operate the monitoring system as an adaptive management tool (not reporting-only), combining KPI time series with narrative cases, stakeholder validation, partner satisfaction surveys, and an annual UEIC Impact Report supported by a digital dashboard.

Next steps should therefore prioritise the Phase 1 foundations—formal governance set-up, launch of the TTO, early infrastructure upgrades, adoption of CoARA-aligned assessment and narrative CV templates, and approval of open science/integrity guidelines—so that Phase 2 can focus on full delivery and Phase 3 on measurable impact and consolidation.

By the end of the period, the Plan’s success should be visible in stronger EU participation and capability (including consortia involvement, staff trained, and improved proposal success rates) alongside verified impact evidence and stakeholder confidence in UEIC as the ecosystem’s practical coordination node.

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ACTION PLANS FOR R&I STRATEGY IMPLEMENTATION, FEUBL, BOSNIA & HERZEGOVINA

1. Executive Summary

The Research and Innovation (R&I) Strategy for the Republic of Srpska and Bosnia and Herzegovina is designed to strengthen the national innovation ecosystem and support the country's gradual integration into the European Research Area (ERA). It is structured around three mutually reinforcing pillars: excellence in research, technology transfer and exploitation, and innovative entrepreneurship. Together, these pillars respond to long-standing challenges—such as very low R&D investment, fragmented governance, weak commercialisation of research and limited support for start-ups—by promoting higher and more effective funding, modern infrastructure, human capital development, and a more favourable environment for innovation-led growth.

To ensure that these pillars can be implemented in a coherent and impactful way, the Strategy is supported by a set of strategic enablers and horizontal initiatives. These include improved governance and coordination across all levels of government, the adoption of a new national R&I strategy aligned with EU priorities, and a stronger role for universities as drivers of research, technology transfer, international cooperation and entrepreneurship. Additional enablers address cultural change, international orientation, stakeholder communication, and the twin transitions of digitalisation and the green economy. Clear roles and responsibilities, measurable indicators and a phased implementation timeline (2026–2028) provide the operational framework for action. Taken together, these elements lay the foundations for a more competitive, sustainable and internationally connected R&I system that can contribute to economic development and EU integration.

2. Key Pillars of the Research and Innovation Strategy

The Research and Innovation Strategy of Republic of Srpska and Bosnia and Herzegovina should be founded upon three interrelated pillars: *excellence in research, technology transfer and exploitation, and innovative entrepreneurship*. These pillars are essential for strengthening the national innovation ecosystem and integrating Bosnia and Herzegovina into the European Research Area (ERA).

2.1. Excellence in Research

The objective is to improve the quality of scientific research, develop human capital and increase participation in international programmes (Horizon Europe, COST, EUREKA). Current allocations for research and development in Bosnia and Herzegovina amount to less than **0.3% of GDP**, among the lowest in Europe, with a fragmented legislative framework and a low number of highly cited publications and patents.

Priorities:

- *Increase public and private investment in R&D* through competitive funds and grants.
- *Establish national and university centres of excellence* equipped with modern infrastructure and laboratories co-financed through EU funds.
- *Promote the development of young researchers* through scholarships, grants and postdoctoral training.
- *Implement a system based on merit-based funding* for scientific projects and reform doctoral studies to enhance quality and relevance.
- *Reduce brain drain* by creating attractive working conditions and fostering collaboration with the diaspora.

2.2. Technology Transfer and Exploitation

Collaboration between science and industry in Bosnia and Herzegovina remains limited, while corporate R&D investments and venture capital are virtually non-existent. Research outputs are rarely commercialised, and the number of patents (47 applications in 2024, of which 34 were domestic) remains exceptionally low.

Priorities:

- *Establish a comprehensive technology transfer system* by developing technology transfer offices (TTOs), incubators, accelerators and science and technology parks.
- *Encourage patents and licensing* through more favourable intellectual property regulations and the implementation of early-stage commercialisation funding programmes (e.g. Proof of Concept).
- *Establish innovation funds* modelled after those in Serbia and North Macedonia, to co-finance joint projects between academia and industry.
- *Implement a smart specialisation strategy (S3)* and concentrate resources on sectors with comparative advantages (e.g. ICT, agri-technologies, renewable energy).
- *Promote the Quintuple Helix model* through regular science-business forums, consortia and joint research agendas.

2.3. Innovative Entrepreneurship

Bosnia and Herzegovina (BiH) is witnessing a growing number of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) engaging in innovation, yet there remains a lack of institutional and financial support for start-ups. The venture capital market is underdeveloped, and state support measures are limited.

Priorities:

- *Create a favourable business environment* through tax incentives for R&D, simplified business registration procedures and the establishment of a legal framework for alternative financing sources (venture capital, crowdfunding, angel investors).
- *Establish a national innovation fund* with a focus on seed funding, mentorship and the development of the start-up ecosystem.
- *Develop business incubators and accelerators* in partnership with universities and local communities.
- *Introduce entrepreneurship education* across all levels of education and strengthen digital skills.
- *Encourage diaspora engagement and private sector involvement* in the investment and mentoring of domestic start-ups.
- *Promote an entrepreneurial culture and reduce the fear of failure* through public campaigns and the celebration of successful domestic entrepreneurs.

For the sustainable development of the innovation ecosystem in BiH, synchronised action by government, universities and the business sector is required, aligned with European standards. Focus must be placed on:

1. Increasing investment in research and development,
2. Strengthening knowledge and technology transfer,
3. Creating an environment that supports innovative entrepreneurship.

These priorities form the foundation of the action plan for the implementation of the R&I Strategy and represent a pathway towards increasing innovation capacity, competitiveness and the integration of BiH into the European Research Area.

3. Strategic Enablers and Key Initiatives

For the implementation of the Research and Innovation Strategy, it is essential to define strategic enablers—intervention areas that will enable the achievement of the established objectives. In the Action Plan, these enablers represent horizontal components that support the pillars of the strategy. What follows is an overview of eight key strategic components (governance, strategy, universities, cultural transformation, international orientation, communication, digital and green transformation), along with proposed initiatives for their implementation. Particular attention is devoted to the context of the Republic of Srpska and Bosnia and Herzegovina, relying on international reports, governmental documents and the experiences of comparable countries.

3.1. Governance

Governance of the research and innovation (R&I) system entails the effective coordination of all levels of government and institutions, clearly defined competences and responsibilities, as well as the establishment of monitoring and accountability mechanisms for policy implementation. At present, the governance of the R&I sector in Bosnia and Herzegovina is highly fragmented—competences are divided between the state level (Ministry of Civil Affairs of Bosnia and Herzegovina), the entities (ministries for science in the Republic of Srpska and the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina) and the cantons in the Federation of BiH, with insufficient coordination. This fragmentation results in overlapping activities, inconsistent measures and inefficient use of resources (European Commission, 2023). The European Commission notes that limited cooperation among the various levels of authority significantly reduces the overall efficiency of the system and prevents even the modest available resources from generating greater impact (European Commission, 2023). In contrast, the Republic of Srpska, which holds competence over the field of science, has established a coordinated and unified governance system through the competent ministry.

As a priority initiative, it is necessary to establish bodies for the coordination of research and innovation policies at various authorised levels in Bosnia and Herzegovina. These bodies (such as national councils for science and innovation) should bring together representatives of all relevant ministries, the academic community and the business sector, serving as forums for the harmonisation of policies and programmes. The Republic of Srpska already has its own coordination structure (the ministry responsible for scientific and technological development), and it is essential to align strategies with other frameworks through regular communication mechanisms.

Moreover, effective financial governance of R&I forms an integral part of this enabler. The current funding system is inadequate—there is no single fund or agency at the state level to finance science, and resources are instead allocated in a fragmented manner across different levels of government. According to the European Commission, the lack of an efficient funding system is one of the factors preventing innovation policy from achieving better results (European Commission, 2023). Consequently, an initiative would be the establishment of consolidated research and innovation funds. This would enhance transparency and enable the financing of larger, joint projects of broader significance, instead of dispersing resources across numerous small-scale calls.

Administrative capacities represent another important aspect of governance. It is necessary to strengthen the capacities of ministries and agencies engaged in R&I policy—through staff training, the introduction of modern project management tools and the implementation of indicator monitoring systems. The success of strategy implementation depends on the ability of institutions to carry it out. In this regard, the introduction of a monitoring and evaluation (M&E) system will enable the tracking of progress through key indicators (e.g. number of start-ups, number of patents, R&D investments, etc.). The M&E system should be integrated into the governance structure—e.g. through the

establishment of a dedicated unit or the engagement of expert organisations that will periodically evaluate the implementation of the action plan.

Regional and EU experiences underscore the importance of strong political support for the field of innovation. Therefore, one of the tasks under governance should be to raise awareness among decision-makers about the significance of R&I for economic development. Regular reports on the state of innovation, to be presented to governments and parliaments, can help ensure that R&I secures a rightful place on the political agenda. In this context, the EU Strategy for the Western Balkans (the so-called Innovation Agenda), adopted by ministers of the region in 2020, envisages the strengthening of innovation governance and joint monitoring of progress (European Commission, 2021). Bosnia and Herzegovina should actively participate in regional coordination mechanisms to adopt best practices in governance. All of the above initiatives are aimed at enabling the coherent and effective implementation of the strategy. Sound governance is the backbone of the strategy—without it, other components risk remaining disconnected and insufficiently effective. Therefore, strengthening governance structures and processes is the first step towards a modern research and innovation system.

3.2. National Strategy for Research and Innovation

The existence of a clear, adopted strategy for research and innovation, accompanied by an action plan, is a fundamental precondition for the targeted development of the sector. In Bosnia and Herzegovina, the previous Strategy for Scientific and Technological Development was valid until 2022; however, its action plan ceased implementation after 2017, and no new document has since been drafted (European Commission, 2023). As a result, the country effectively operated without a valid science development plan during the period 2017–2023—a situation noted in European Commission reports, which state that from 2017 to 2023, no action plan was in place. Consequently, policies were ad hoc, fragmented, and reactive rather than proactive. This state of affairs contributed to further stagnation—the innovation gap between Bosnia and Herzegovina and the European Union continues to widen year after year (European Commission, 2023).

The Republic of Srpska has adopted the Strategy for the Development of Science and Technology, Higher Education and the Information Society for the period 2023–2029. In Sarajevo Canton, a draft Strategy for Science Development 2025–2028 has been published. Innovation and digitalisation have been identified as the leading accelerator in the Development Strategy of the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina for the period 2021–2027. The European Commission recommends that Bosnia and Herzegovina adopt a new science development strategy and accompanying action plan as a matter of priority (European Commission, 2023). This document should define a vision, priority areas (preferably based on a smart specialisation analysis) and concrete measures, including designated implementers and deadlines. The drafting process must involve all relevant stakeholders (ministries at the level of The Republic of Srpska, the Federation of BiH and the cantons, as well as academia, industry and civil society) to ensure that the strategy functions as a roadmap for the further development of science.

Furthermore, alignment with EU frameworks must be ensured—the strategy should reflect the goals of the European Research Area (ERA), the Green Agenda for the Western Balkans and the Digital Agenda, thereby demonstrating Bosnia and Herzegovina's commitment to European priorities (European Commission, 2021). It is advisable for the strategy to include defined strategic objectives and indicators. For example, targets may include increasing R&D investment to 1% of GDP by 2030, doubling the number of innovative start-ups over five years and raising the number of international scientific publications by a specific percentage. Each of these objectives should have measurable indicators to be tracked through the action plan. Good practice suggests setting interim goals (e.g. for 2027 and 2029) to monitor trends and adjust policies accordingly.

A particularly important segment—the Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3)—should be integrated into or developed as a parallel document to the national strategy. The European Commission emphasises that the development of S3 in Bosnia and Herzegovina is still in its early stages, and that its absence negatively impacts activities in the field of research and innovation (European Commission, 2023). The S3 methodology assists in identifying narrowly defined priority areas based on competitive advantages (e.g. wood processing with the application of new technologies, the IT sector in agriculture, medical sciences, etc.). The Republic of Srpska has initiated activities on S3 and identified certain niches (e.g. in agriculture – agrotech) (Ministry for Scientific and Technological Development, Higher Education and the Information Society of The Republic of Srpska, 2019), but it is necessary to complete this process and ensure the coordination of entity-level specialisations. An initiative would be to accelerate the finalisation of the smart specialisation process with support from the JRC of the European Commission and to incorporate its findings into the national strategy.

Following the adoption of the strategy, its implementation and monitoring are of critical importance. The action plan must define the responsible parties for each task, deadlines, success indicators and funding sources. A good practice example is Serbia, which, after adopting its strategy for scientific development 2016–2020, developed a detailed action plan and regularly monitored implementation through annual reports, leading to the majority of measures being implemented by 2020. Bosnia and Herzegovina should adopt a similar approach: for instance, forming an operational working group (or using the aforementioned Science Council) that would meet every six months to review the implementation of the action plan, identify delays and propose adjustments.

Finally, the strategy will not have an impact if it remains a “dead letter”. Therefore, it is essential to ensure its political adoption at a high level and a clear commitment to its implementation. Moreover, international support (EU Delegation, UNESCO, UNDP) can be mobilised to support the implementation through technical assistance projects and funding for specific measures. The strategy is foundational—a key enabler without which other initiatives lack a coherent framework. Its development and implementation must therefore be regarded as a strategic priority among the enabling mechanisms.

3.3. Universities

Universities and higher education institutions lie at the heart of the research and innovation system—they generate new knowledge (through research) and train new professionals (through education). Universities must assume a more proactive role in implementing the innovation strategy. At present, they face numerous challenges, including low levels of research activity, limited science funding, outdated curricula insufficiently aligned with labour market needs and a lack of international recognition. Accreditation and quality assurance also remain problematic—the European Commission notes that the system of accreditation for higher education institutions is still not fully functional at the level of Bosnia and Herzegovina (European Commission, 2023), which indirectly affects the quality of scientific work.

To transform universities into drivers of innovation, reforms in higher education are necessary to stimulate research and strengthen links with industry. First, the research activities of academic staff must be encouraged. In the current system, teaching staff are burdened with teaching and administrative duties, and academic promotion is not always strictly tied to research output. An initiative would be to introduce criteria that evaluate scientific performance (publications, patents, project leadership) in promotion procedures and to allocate time and resources to achieve these results. For example, introducing a “one teaching-free day per week” rule for academics to focus exclusively on research, or providing internal university grants to launch research projects led by young researchers.

Second, universities must strengthen ties with industry. This involves establishing partnerships with companies—joint laboratories, commissioned research projects and the involvement of practitioners in the teaching process. Faculties in technical and natural sciences, in particular, should develop so-called Living Lab models, in which students and professors work on solving real-world industrial problems. In The Republic of Srpska, such practices are already emerging—for example, the Faculty of Technology in Banja Luka collaborates with local companies in the food industry—but these efforts need to be systematised and extended across all disciplines.

Third, it is essential to actively promote entrepreneurship within universities. This entails facilitating the establishment of spin-off companies by professors and students (by defining rules that allow inventions created at the university to be commercially exploited, with revenue-sharing arrangements between the inventor and the institution). To make this feasible, legislation must be adopted to support such activities (modelled, for instance, on the legal framework in Italy). Additionally, each university could establish a Centre for Innovation and Entrepreneurship offering advisory support to individuals wishing to launch a business based on university research. For instance, the University of Sarajevo established such a centre in cooperation with an Italian university, resulting in increased student interest in start-up activities. At the Faculty of Economics, University of Banja Luka, the Centre for Project Management and Entrepreneurship (CPME) has been active since 2014 and has contributed to the creation of student-founded start-ups.

Fourth, the internationalisation of universities is a key component of knowledge acquisition and diffusion within the framework of Open Innovation—a new paradigm of collaboration among universities, industry, research and development centres, institutions, citizens, and other stakeholders in innovation and research. Participation in international research projects (such as Horizon Europe, COST Actions, Erasmus+ for researcher exchange) brings not only financial resources but also new expertise. Universities in Bosnia and Herzegovina have already started engaging—for example, under the Horizon 2020 programme, Bosnia and Herzegovina participated in over 100 collaboration agreements with EU research teams (European Commission, 2023). This figure needs to be increased through better support for project applications (e.g. offering training in project writing, establishing project support offices at every university—as has been done at UNIBL with the Centre for Research Development and Support). The Commission notes an encouraging development—Bosnian researchers secured approximately EUR 1.65 million from Horizon Europe in 2021 and around EUR 2.1 million in 2022, demonstrating growing capacity (European Commission, 2023). This trend should continue—the target could be for each faculty to have at least one EU-funded project by the end of the strategy period.

Fifth, universities must also play a role in promoting scientific literacy and a culture of innovation in society. Through open science events, cooperation with secondary schools (e.g. “young researchers” programmes) and science popularisation, universities contribute to creating a favourable innovation climate. Strategically, universities are expected to support the implementation of practically all pillars of the strategy—thus, they must be viewed as implementation partners, not merely as policy subjects. This means that university representatives should be included in all bodies monitoring implementation (such as the previously mentioned Science and Innovation Council).

Ultimately, investing in universities is an investment in the future of innovation. The Republic of Srpska has recognised this through initiatives such as the establishment of new laboratories at the University of Banja Luka, but long-term sustainability requires systemic support. Recommended measures include establishing dedicated funds for university research, reforming higher education financing towards a performance-based model and fostering collaborative projects among universities in Bosnia and Herzegovina (to reduce fragmentation between the academic communities of the two entities). Only strong and interconnected universities can generate the critical mass of knowledge needed for a genuine innovation leap.

3.4. Cultural Change

In the context of innovation, culture refers to the set of values, attitudes and norms that foster creativity, collaboration and readiness for change. In Bosnia and Herzegovina, there is substantial scope for enhancing innovation culture—traditional bureaucratic heritage and rigid structures often stifle entrepreneurial spirit and freedom of research. The strategic enabler “cultural change” therefore targets a transformation in the mindset across institutions, the economy and society at large, to promote innovation, openness and acceptance of risk.

One key aspect is the organisational culture within public research institutions. At present, many institutes and faculties are hierarchically structured, with insufficient incentives for young researchers and for interdisciplinary work. An initiative would be to introduce programmes that reward teamwork and results—such as annual awards for innovative projects, financial bonuses for research groups achieving patents or practical outputs and similar measures. Furthermore, institutions must encourage experimentation and tolerance for failure. In innovation, it is normal for many ideas to fail; rather than penalising failure, institutions should learn from mistakes and try again. Changing this mindset can be supported through leadership training and the introduction of more flexible rules for projects (e.g. funding pilot projects even if outcomes are uncertain).

Anti-corruption measures and meritocracy are also part of cultural change. Innovation thrives in environments where the most competent and creative individuals progress—not those with the strongest connections. It is essential to ensure that funding for research and innovation is allocated transparently, based on expert evaluation. This builds trust in the system. Efforts by public authorities to improve innovation policies and activities are starting to yield results, but systemic cooperation among all actors remains necessary (European Commission, 2023). Transparency and accountability—such as publicly publishing project outcomes, use of funds and their impact—should become the norm. This represents a cultural shift towards more open governance.

Cross-sectoral and inter-institutional collaboration also has a cultural dimension. At present, barriers between academia and industry are partly cultural—stemming from differences in language, mutual distrust and lack of familiarity. A culture of trust and partnership must be cultivated. One initiative could be the establishment of dialogue platforms (regular meetings, conferences) where researchers and business representatives exchange ideas. Through ongoing communication, understanding is built and stereotypes broken (e.g. businesses often perceive universities as overly theoretical, while universities feel industry does not value science—the truth lies somewhere in between, and collaboration benefits both sides).

At a broader level, public awareness of the importance of science and innovation must grow. Cultural change also entails the public beginning to view scientists and innovators as drivers of development and supporting investment in this field. The media can play a role by promoting the achievements of domestic innovators. Moreover, creativity must be encouraged in the education system from an early age—through project-based learning, robotics and coding competitions, and science camps for secondary school pupils. These are small building blocks that shape a pro-innovation culture among new generations.

A vital part of cultural change is also gender equality and inclusivity in innovation. It is necessary to actively involve women in STEM fields and ensure equal opportunities for all, regardless of background. Bosnia and Herzegovina already has a relatively high share of women in science (e.g. among academic staff), but they are often underrepresented in leadership positions in research. Targeted measures—such as mentorship programmes for young female researchers and highlighting successful female scientists as role models—help to break down cultural prejudices.

Maintaining high ethical standards and practising responsible research (the so-called Responsible Research and Innovation – RRI concept) is also part of this cultural dimension. The WBC-RRI.NET project has promoted future scenarios for responsible research in Bosnia and Herzegovina and the region by involving society in innovation through the quadruple helix approach. Cultural

change means that scientists and innovators consider the societal impacts of their activities from the outset, leading to more sustainable and socially accepted innovations.

To initiate these cultural changes, the strategy should incorporate educational and promotional activities: seminars for institutional leaders on innovation management, awareness-raising campaigns and specific reforms in internal organisational practices (e.g. universities could revise internal regulations to reward collaborative projects between departments, which is currently uncommon). Culture changes slowly, but it is strategically vital to sow the seeds of these transformations from the very beginning of the strategy's implementation—without cultural support, structural reforms are likely to face resistance or remain underutilised.

3.5. International Orientation

International orientation refers to the readiness and ability of the domestic research and innovation (R&I) ecosystem to integrate into global flows of knowledge, collaboration and markets. For a relatively small country such as Bosnia and Herzegovina, internationalisation is of critical importance—it provides access to greater funding sources, opportunities to learn from best practices and integration into European innovation networks. Encouragingly, recent progress has been made: since 2021, Bosnia and Herzegovina has been an associated country to the Horizon Europe programme, granting its researchers and innovators full participation rights in the EU's largest R&I programme (European Commission, 2023). In the very first year, significant results were achieved—with €1.65 million competitively secured in 2021, and preliminary data for 2022 showing an increase to over €2.1 million (European Commission, 2023). These achievements, although modest in absolute terms, prove that BiH researchers are capable of competing at the European level and should be further encouraged to do so.

Strategic initiatives within the international orientation component include, first and foremost, the optimal utilisation of EU programmes. Beyond Horizon Europe, these also include COST (researcher networks), EUREKA (industry-oriented applied research), Erasmus+ (mobility and capacity building in higher education), among others. Bosnia and Herzegovina should establish national contact points and dedicated support teams for each of these programmes in order to increase participation rates. In the region, Serbia serves as a good example—as an associated country, it secured over €150 million from Horizon 2020 between 2014 and 2020, while Bosnia and Herzegovina attracted around €8.6 million (European Commission, 2023). This discrepancy is partly due to better support infrastructure and stronger promotion of international opportunities in Serbia. Therefore, BiH must close this gap by investing in awareness-raising and researcher training for project proposal writing.

International orientation also entails regional cooperation within the Western Balkans. A common Regional Strategy for Science and Innovation was adopted in 2013 by the region's ministers, promoting joint mobilisation of resources and knowledge (World Bank, 2013). Bosnia and Herzegovina actively participates in initiatives such as the Western Balkans Platform on Research and Innovation and various regional projects (e.g. via the RCC). These efforts should be continued and deepened—for example, through joint calls for research proposals between BiH and neighbouring countries, or intra-regional researcher exchanges. Regional cooperation serves as a stepping stone toward integration into the wider European community and helps countries in similar positions to strengthen their capacities collectively.

The inclusion of the diaspora is a unique opportunity to be seized. Bosnia and Herzegovina has a considerable scientific and professional diaspora around the world—experts working in leading universities and companies. Initiatives such as “Brain Gain” programmes or diaspora scientist networks can facilitate knowledge transfer and partnerships. For instance, Serbia's “Returning Point” programme links overseas professionals with domestic institutions; Bosnia and Herzegovina could

develop a similar portal and fund to financially support collaborative projects with the diaspora (e.g. guest lectures, start-up mentorship, joint research projects).

Promoting domestic innovations in foreign markets is another crucial aspect of internationalisation. Innovative enterprises from BiH must compete globally in order to grow. Governments at both state and entity levels can support this by organising delegations to international technology fairs, connecting start-ups with foreign investors (e.g. through events like “Investor Days” inviting international VC funds). Additionally, joining international innovation hub networks—such as the European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT)—creates new opportunities. In this regard, it is encouraging that BiH has been included in the EIT Regional Innovation Scheme from 2025 (European Commission, 2023), enabling domestic actors to participate in EIT initiatives for capacity building and projects in areas such as climate innovation, digital technologies and more.

International orientation also refers to alignment of domestic policies with international standards. This includes participation in the European Research Area (ERA)—for example, embracing principles of open science, researcher mobility (e.g. removing barriers to recognition of diplomas and international experience) and more. The European Commission emphasises that integration into the new ERA supports national R&I reforms (European Commission, 2021). One potential initiative would be the development of a National ERA Accession Agenda, identifying BiH’s current position with respect to key ERA priorities (such as the free movement of researchers and knowledge, gender equality in science, synergy with EU Structural Funds, etc.) and outlining the measures needed to meet these requirements.

Ultimately, international orientation must become an integral part of every component—universities should have international strategies, research institutes should seek partners abroad and companies should target EU markets. A success indicator for this enabler will be, among others, Bosnia and Herzegovina’s progress on global innovation indices. In recent years, the Global Innovation Index (GII) ranked BiH in the 70s and 80s (e.g. 70th in 2022), but with meaningful internationalisation and investment, improvement is possible—Serbia, for example, reached 55th place, partly due to stronger international engagement. Therefore, BiH should aim for similar advancement, using international orientation as a lever for accelerating the development of its innovation system.

3.6. Stakeholders’ Communication

Stakeholder communication is a horizontal enabler that ensures all ecosystem actors—researchers, businesses, policymakers, civil society and citizens—are informed, engaged and coordinated in the process of strategy implementation. Effective communication builds trust, facilitates two-way information exchange (top-down and bottom-up) and ensures that policies align with real needs on the ground.

One of the initial steps involves establishing mechanisms for consultation and dialogue. This means that, when defining actions and reforms under the strategy, relevant stakeholders should be consulted. For example, before adopting new laws or funding programmes, public consultations or focus groups should be conducted with representatives of universities, chambers of commerce, associations of innovative enterprises and NGOs active in the technology sector. This approach not only enhances the quality of policies (by incorporating practical insights), but also increases their acceptance during implementation.

Such dialogue can be institutionalised through the formation of permanent working groups or advisory bodies. For instance, an Innovation Council comprising representatives from academia, industry and civil society could periodically issue recommendations to governments on strategy implementation. Likewise, sector-specific platforms (e.g. digital, agro-innovation, health innovation) would allow experts in particular domains to communicate their needs and ideas to policymakers. The European practice of the quadruple helix model—where civil society is included alongside

government, academia and business—demonstrates that broader participation leads to more sustainable and socially acceptable innovations (Đonlagić Alibegović et al., 2022).

A particular aspect of communication is the promotion and dissemination of information about opportunities offered through the strategy. Often, actors are unaware of available support programmes, grants or training. A dedicated communication campaign should be developed to clearly convey strategic messages to target groups. This might include: the development of a central innovation portal (aggregating all news, calls and events in the R&I domain), regular newsletters for researchers and businesses, and the use of social media to highlight success stories. For example, when a research team secures a Horizon project or a company develops a patent, this should be publicised—sending a signal to the community that positive developments are occurring and motivating others to engage.

Communication must be two-way: it is essential to establish channels through which stakeholders can provide feedback to authorities and strategy implementers. This could involve periodic surveys or satisfaction assessments (e.g. annual surveys measuring business satisfaction with innovation support—according to the European Commission, businesses in BiH are currently the least satisfied in the Western Balkans with the level of digitalisation in public services (European Commission, 2023), which is a crucial feedback point for policymakers). Additionally, formal channels such as an online platform where companies can report barriers they encounter (e.g. regulatory obstacles to innovation) would help identify and address problems during action plan implementation.

In The Republic of Srpska and the Federation of BiH, chambers of commerce and business associations can play a pivotal role in stakeholder communication. They should be actively involved as partners in promoting the innovation agenda. For instance, the Chamber of Commerce of The Republic of Srpska could establish a dedicated section for innovation and digital transformation, bringing together companies interested in the topic and facilitating the flow of information between public authorities and businesses.

The role of media and public discourse should not be overlooked. Creating a “positive narrative” around innovation in the public sphere will help generate broader societal support. As noted in the cultural enabler, the popularisation of science overlaps with public communication. Organising events such as science and innovation festivals, television programmes featuring locally developed technologies and involving prominent figures (e.g. successful diaspora innovators) as innovation ambassadors are all ways to make the strategy “alive” and relevant to citizens.

Ultimately, well-designed communication ensures that all actors feel part of the same team working toward the transformation of a knowledge-based economy. When the private sector sees that it can reach the government with a proposal and be heard, when scientists feel that their voice is acknowledged in programme development, and when citizens perceive that innovation serves the common good, then a healthy climate of trust is established. In such a climate, the implementation of all other strategy components flows more smoothly because there is a shared vision and support—this is the ultimate goal of this strategic enabler.

3.7. Digital Transformation

Digital transformation is an indispensable component of a modern innovation system. It entails the adoption of digital technologies across all sectors of the economy, the digitalisation of public services, the development of digital skills and infrastructure, as well as the creation of new digital products and services. For Bosnia and Herzegovina, digital transformation represents both a major challenge and a significant opportunity. The challenge lies in the current level of digitalisation, which lags behind the EU: business sector surveys highlight dissatisfaction with e-government and the digital environment – as many as 60% of small enterprises lack even a basic website, while only around 18% actively engage in e-commerce (European Commission, 2023). Furthermore, the implementation of e-government is

hampered by political disunity and the absence of harmonised standards at the state level (European Commission, 2023). However, the opportunity lies in the fact that digital technologies can bypass certain stages of development and accelerate progress: with relatively modest investment, digital platforms can connect innovators from Bosnia and Herzegovina with global markets.

Strategic initiatives for digital transformation must operate on several fronts. Firstly, the development of digital infrastructure – high-speed broadband internet, particularly in rural areas, data centres and similar facilities. Without robust infrastructure, digitalisation is unsustainable. This requires investment and public-private partnerships (e.g. telecom operators, supported by governments, could expand network coverage). Secondly, the enhancement of digital skills within the population. Bosnia and Herzegovina faces a shortage of ICT professionals, which directly limits innovation (the lack of competitive human capital and availability of ICT personnel has been identified as a barrier to digital innovation). It is necessary to modernise educational curricula – introducing programming and digital literacy from primary school onwards, expanding STEM streams in secondary schools and increasing enrolment in IT and related faculties. Additionally, reskilling and adult training (e.g. IT sector retraining programmes) can relatively quickly generate a new wave of digital entrepreneurs.

Thirdly, the focus must be on the digitalisation of micro, small and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs). Most MSMEs in Bosnia and Herzegovina have not yet adopted modern digital tools – such as e-business, cloud computing or data analytics (Centre for Policy Evaluation and Research, 2022). One initiative would be to launch a “Digitalise MSMEs” programme that offers technical and financial assistance to companies seeking to implement digital solutions. This could include vouchers for software acquisition, subsidised consultancy for digital transformation or the establishment of Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs). DIHs are centres where companies can test technologies and receive guidance (an EU concept increasingly applied in candidate countries). Bosnia and Herzegovina should establish at least one DIH in each entity, focusing on key industries (e.g. one for manufacturing, one for the IT sector), which has already begun with the establishment of such hubs.

Fourthly, the improvement of e-government and digital public services. This is the responsibility of the authorities, but it has a direct impact on the innovation ecosystem – efficient e-government reduces administrative burdens for innovative companies. The European Commission notes that the development of e-services in Bosnia and Herzegovina is slow due to a lack of regulatory harmonisation across government levels, the absence of a unified framework for e-signatures and e-identification, and weak coordination (European Commission, 2023). The initiatives are clear: a state-level law on electronic identification and digital services should be adopted (aligned with EU standards such as the eIDAS Regulation); a unified digital identity for citizens, valid across the entire country, should be established; and registers and databases across entities and cantons should be integrated. Projects such as the One-Stop-Shop for businesses (enabling entrepreneurs to register a company, report taxes and contributions online, etc.) should be prioritised. These measures not only improve the business environment but also generate large volumes of data that can subsequently be utilised for innovation (open data initiatives).

Fifthly, digital transformation must be supported through cybersecurity and a suitable legal framework. As more business activity moves online, cybersecurity becomes imperative. Research has shown that MSMEs in Bosnia and Herzegovina are often unaware of the importance of cybersecurity and perceive it as an expensive investment (Centre for Policy Evaluation and Research, 2022). The action plan should provide for awareness-raising activities on cyber hygiene and even co-financing of security solutions in companies. In parallel, laws governing digital business (electronic signatures, data protection – e.g. GDPR implementation, digital banking, payment services) must be modernised to facilitate the flourishing of innovations such as fintech, e-commerce and others.

A potentially valuable initiative is the establishment of a national digital platform serving as a central hub for digital transformation support. As suggested by recent research, an online platform should be developed to match supply and demand for digital solutions in Bosnia and Herzegovina –

whereby MSMEs could find domestic IT companies offering relevant products/services, thereby stimulating the local digital ecosystem (Centre for Policy Evaluation and Research, 2022). Such a platform could also offer educational content, tutorials and similar resources. The report by the Centre for Policy Evaluation (2022) recommends a range of measures: from financial support for MSME digitalisation and awareness-raising, to the elimination of regulatory barriers (e.g. costly payment processing and postal fees for e-commerce) – all of which should be incorporated into the action plan.

Ultimately, success indicators for digital transformation will include an increase in the proportion of digitally active enterprises, growth in e-commerce and improved positioning on digitalisation indices (e.g. the EU's Digital Economy and Society Index – DESI). At present, Bosnia and Herzegovina ranks among the lowest in Europe by these indicators, but with focused efforts, significant progress could be achieved by the end of the strategy implementation period. This would lay the groundwork for participation in global Industry 4.0 trends – where digital technologies such as artificial intelligence, the Internet of Things and big data are driving innovation. If Bosnia and Herzegovina succeeds in keeping pace with digital transformation, its innovators will be better positioned to compete and connect with the world, which, combined with other enablers, will lead to a sustainable innovation ecosystem.

3.8. Green Transformation

Green transformation refers to the transition towards a sustainable, low-carbon and resource-efficient economy, in line with the principles of environmental protection and climate change mitigation. For Bosnia and Herzegovina, the green agenda is of paramount importance, as the economy remains heavily reliant on hydrocarbon energy (coal, oil) and energy-intensive industry. Data show that Bosnia and Herzegovina has the highest energy intensity of GDP in the region – consuming around 6.7 MJ of energy per dollar of GDP, which is twice the EU average (Ignjatović et al., 2024). Moreover, CO₂ emissions per unit of GDP are the highest compared to neighbouring countries (Ignjatović et al., 2024), due to reliance on outdated lignite-fired thermal power plants (Bosnia and Herzegovina operates five large thermal plants with a combined capacity of approximately 2,000 MW that emit enormous quantities of CO₂ and pollutants) (Ignjatović et al., 2024). This trend is unsustainable – both ecologically and economically: the EU is introducing mechanisms such as the CBAM (Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism), which will impose levies on products with high carbon footprints (Ignjatović et al., 2024), making exports from Bosnia and Herzegovina more expensive on EU markets if no action is taken.

The green transformation is therefore both an obligation and an opportunity. Bosnia and Herzegovina signed the Sofia Declaration on the Green Agenda for the Western Balkans (2020), assuming commitments in five areas: energy decarbonisation, circular economy, pollution reduction, sustainable agriculture and biodiversity protection (Balkans Fund for Strategic Research, 2021). However, fulfilling these commitments requires concrete steps. The key initiatives under this enabler include:

Energy transition. The gradual phasing-out of coal and shift towards renewable energy sources (RES), along with improved energy efficiency. Bosnia and Herzegovina has set a target for 43.6% of electricity to come from RES by 2030 (Ignjatović et al., 2024), with the current share already at around 37–38% due to hydroelectric plants. It is necessary to accelerate investment in solar and wind energy – although entities have initiated RES auctions, procedures should be expedited and bureaucratic obstacles removed. Investment in energy-efficient infrastructure (e.g. building insulation, more efficient district heating systems) also holds vast potential. The European Commission recommends drafting and implementing a building renovation strategy to improve energy savings (European Commission, 2023). Innovation plays a role here through the development of local solutions, such as smart grids that integrate RES, energy storage systems (batteries) and similar. Scientific and technological institutions in Bosnia and Herzegovina could focus on adapting these technologies (e.g.

the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering in Sarajevo is developing solar collector prototypes adapted to local conditions). The action plan should support such projects.

Circular economy. Transitioning from the linear model (“take – make – dispose”) to a circular one, where waste is minimised and resources are recycled and reused. This is especially relevant in the waste and materials management sector. Initiatives may include support for innovation in recycling, biomaterials, energy valorisation of waste and more. Research indicates that resource productivity in the Western Balkans is five times lower than in the EU (Ignjatović et al., 2024), implying enormous material value is being wasted. Innovations in packaging, processing industrial waste into secondary raw materials, and similar measures can simultaneously protect the environment and create new jobs. Action plans for the circular economy should be developed, and innovative companies (e.g. those producing furniture from recycled wood or biofuels from waste) should be supported both financially and through public promotion.

Sustainable mobility and transport. Innovations in electromobility, alternative-fuel public transport and smart transport systems are part of the green transformation. Bosnia and Herzegovina has yet to make significant strides in this area – the number of electric vehicles is negligible, incentives for their purchase are lacking and charging infrastructure is underdeveloped. The action plan may include measures such as: tax reliefs for electric vehicle imports, pilot projects introducing electric buses in urban areas and the development of domestic capacities (e.g. technical universities could work on solar charger prototypes, vehicle conversion to electric drive, etc.). Horizon Europe provides funding opportunities for Green Deal projects – Bosnia and Herzegovina should actively seek partnerships in such consortia.

Green innovations in industry and agriculture. Traditional industries (metallurgy, chemical, wood processing) must innovate to reduce emissions and resource use. Technologies such as carbon capture and storage, replacing fossil fuels with hydrogen in industrial processes, and precision agriculture (optimising fertiliser and water use) are all innovations that should be encouraged. Research institutes and companies should collaborate on demonstration projects. For example, in Slovenia, a pilot project to replace coke with wood waste in steel production has produced favourable CO₂ reduction outcomes; Bosnia and Herzegovina could learn from this and test similar innovations in its own industries.

Strengthening institutional capacity for green transition. As emphasised by Ignjatović et al. (2024), the greatest challenge of the green transition lies not only in technology but in institutional reform and policy coordination. It is essential to better align energy, industrial, agricultural and innovation policies with green goals. In practice, this means involving Ministries of Ecology and Energy in innovation bodies, and conversely, including the academic community in energy strategy development and explicitly accounting for the role of innovation. The European Commission observes that the lack of a unified regulatory framework for investment in the low-carbon energy sector is hampering progress – for instance, the absence of a national energy regulatory agency hinders the attraction of RES investment (European Commission, 2023). This is an institutional reform that must be considered.

Despite the challenges, the green transformation represents a development opportunity. Investments in renewables and green technologies create new jobs (e.g. the RES sector is labour-intensive during construction), increase energy independence and reduce long-term costs. Additionally, as part of EU integration, Bosnia and Herzegovina will be required to meet specific green criteria – it is better to proactively pursue transformation than to face future penalties or trade barriers. One positive signal is that Sarajevo has been included in the European Mission for Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities by 2030 (European Commission, 2023), meaning it will receive technical assistance and funding to accelerate green investments in the urban context. This experience may serve as a model for other cities in Bosnia and Herzegovina.

Ultimately, the success of the green transformation will be measured by reductions in emissions, increases in the share of renewable energy and improvements in environmental quality

(cleaner air and water, fewer waste landfills). Yet beyond these quantitative indicators, a crucial outcome will be a shift in mindset – among citizens, the economy and authorities – that ecology and economy go hand in hand. Innovation is the tool that can facilitate this synergy, and through a strategic approach, Bosnia and Herzegovina can avoid being held back by green transitions and instead modernise its economy through green innovation, creating better jobs for the future (Ignjatović et al., 2024).

4. Roles and Responsibilities

The effective implementation of the research and innovation strategy requires clearly defined roles and responsibilities of all relevant stakeholders – from state institutions and academia to research organisations, the private sector and civil society.

Strategies in this domain establish goals and development priorities for science, technological progress and the application of innovative solutions, but their successful implementation depends on the coordinated and accountable engagement of all involved actors. In this context, understanding and precisely determining the roles and responsibilities represents the foundation for establishing a functional and effective system of support for research and innovation.

Table 7: Mapping of stakeholders

STAKEHOLDERS	ROLE	RESPONSIBILITIES WITHIN THE ACTION PLAN
Government institutions (ministries, agencies)	Decision-makers and strategy coordinators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Defining national priorities – Drafting and implementing the legislative framework – Providing public funding – Evaluating outcomes and policies
Policy-makers (expert groups, advisory bodies)	Policy design based on analysis and evidence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Analysing the needs of the R&I sector – Drafting policy proposals – Recommending incentive measures – Advising government institutions
Investors (VC funds, business angels)	Financial support for innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Investing in start-ups and technologies – Collaborating with the R&D sector – Mentoring and advising start-ups – Establishing specialised funds
Science and technology parks (STPs) and innovation hubs	Infrastructure and support for R&D and technology transfer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Providing conditions for start-up development – Connecting science, industry and academia – Organising support programmes – Promoting technology transfer
Incubators and accelerators	Support for early-stage business development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Identification of innovative teams – Training and mentoring – Networking with investors – Market access and capacity growth
Universities and research institutions	Drivers of research and human resource development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Conducting research – Educating qualified personnel – Developing technology transfer offices – Collaborating with the business sector and the EU

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Designing and implementing research projects – Upholding ethical and social responsibility
Start-ups and innovative SMEs	Innovation and commercialisation drivers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Developing new solutions and products – Participating in projects and funding programmes – Providing feedback on needs and barriers – Testing innovations in practice
Private sector	Partner in the application of research results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Collaborating with the R&D sector – Investing in innovation – Employing skilled personnel – Defining market needs
Civil society organisations (NGOs, foundations)	Bridging science and society	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Promoting socially responsible innovation – Participating in public consultations – Monitoring the impact of innovation – Involving the civil sector (citizens) in the development of public R&I policies by fostering so-called “social innovation”

Notes. The table presents the stakeholders relevant for the effective implementation of the research and innovation strategy.

The roles of stakeholders are integrated into the action plans of the research and innovation strategy, structured according to:

- the strategic priority areas,
- the implementation timeframe,
- performance indicators, and
- the responsible stakeholders.

Strategic priority areas – The Action Plan elaborates the strategic goals by thematic or sectoral priorities, within which the key actors for the implementation of specific activities are identified.

Implementation timeframe – Each activity is assigned a clear time horizon (short-term, medium-term, long-term or a concrete deadline), which enables monitoring of implementation dynamics and the setting of realistic deadlines for achieving the planned results.

Performance indicators (output and outcome indicators) – Clearly defined quantitative and qualitative indicators allow for the measurement of progress and success in implementation (e.g. number of completed projects, number of researchers involved in cooperation with industry, number of patents, level of citizen engagement, etc.).

Responsible stakeholders – Each activity is assigned a specific responsible institution or group of actors, thereby ensuring accountability, coordination and implementation monitoring.

In this way, an integrated and transparent approach to the implementation of the strategy is achieved, enabling all stakeholders to clearly understand their role, obligations and contribution to the achievement of common goals. At the same time, such a structure of the action plans facilitates monitoring, evaluation and adjustment of measures in accordance with changes in the environment and the needs of the system.

The alignment of European Union development policies with those at all levels of government in Bosnia and Herzegovina represents one of the key preconditions for the successful integration of the country into the European development framework. Given the multi-layered administrative and political structure of BiH, the harmonisation process faces numerous challenges stemming from

fragmented competences, insufficiently developed coordination mechanisms, as well as varying institutional capacities at the state, entity, cantonal and local levels.

The specificities of the political and institutional structure of BiH require a unified approach to strategies in the field of research and innovation – based on inter-entity cooperation, alignment of priorities and strengthening the role of all relevant actors, including academia, the business sector and civil society. Although burdened with numerous obstacles, these processes also represent an opportunity to build a functional, decentralised, yet coordinated system for scientific and innovation development, which can contribute to stronger and faster integration into the European Research Area (ERA).

5. Timeline and Milestones

The presented plan is based on the strategic priorities defined within the national policy on science, technological development and innovation, with the aim of establishing a competitive, sustainable and internationally integrated research and innovation ecosystem.

The Gantt chart provides a visual representation of the implementation dynamics of strategic measures and priorities within the Action Plan for Research and Innovation. It offers a clear overview of the sequence, duration and interlinkages of activities during the initial three-year implementation period (2026–2028), thereby facilitating planning, coordination and progress monitoring.

Within this plan, activities are structured according to implementation phases encompassing the full cycle from preparation to evaluation:

- **Planning and establishment** – setting the institutional and programmatic foundations for implementing the strategy;
- **Implementation and development** – operational execution of the planned measures and activities;
- **Consolidation and evaluation** – assessment of the results achieved and reinforcement of system sustainability.

Explanation of implementation phases:

➤ **Phase I: *Initiation of Activities***

This phase involves the initiation of institutional, planning and regulatory processes.

Activities include:

- ✓ Excellence in Research – preparation and launch of new R&D funds and grants, development of a model for centres of excellence, reform of doctoral studies.
- ✓ Technology Transfer – mapping of potential and planning for the development of Technology Transfer Offices (TTOs), analysis of intellectual property regulations, drafting of the Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3).
- ✓ Innovative Entrepreneurship – amendments to tax regulations, establishment of a national innovation fund and development of partnerships with universities for incubators.
- ✓ R&I System Governance – establishment of the National Council and development of the M&E system methodology.
- ✓ Digital and Green Transformation – initial planning of digital infrastructure and development of plans for renewable energy sources (RES) and the circular economy.

Table 8: Chronological overview of the implementation of reform initiatives in the R&I system (Gantt chart 2026–2028)

Year	2026												2027												2028											
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
KEY PILLAR	ACTIVITY																																			
Excellence in Research	Expansion of existing and establishment of new funds and grants for R&D and young researchers																																			
	Establishment of national and university centres of excellence																																			
	Reform of doctoral studies																																			
	Cooperation with the diaspora																																			

➤ **Phase II: Development and Full Implementation**

This is the phase in which activities transition from planning to implementation:

- ✓ Excellence in Research – awarding of grants, establishment of centres of excellence, implementation of reformed doctoral programmes and cooperation with the diaspora.
- ✓ Technology Transfer – establishment and implementation of TTOs, innovation funds and pilot implementation of the S3 strategy.
- ✓ Innovative Entrepreneurship – launch of accelerators, implementation of entrepreneurship education, development of a diaspora mentoring network.
- ✓ System Governance – functioning of the Council, testing of the M&E system.
- ✓ Digital Transformation – delivery of training programmes, development of e-services and digitalisation of SMEs through the “Digitalise SMEs” programme.
- ✓ Green Transformation – implementation of investments in RES and energy efficiency programme.

➤ **Phase III: Operational Results**

This phase marks stabilisation and the achievement of measurable results:

- ✓ Excellence in Research – consolidation of research funds, international networking of centres of excellence and evaluation of doctoral reform outcomes.
- ✓ Technology Transfer – stable functioning of the TTO network, expansion of innovation funds and strengthening of intellectual property protection.
- ✓ Innovative Entrepreneurship – continued funding of start-ups, linkage with investment funds and monitoring of impact.
- ✓ System Governance – full implementation of the M&E system and evaluation of the Council’s performance.
- ✓ Digital Transformation – expansion and optimisation of digital platforms, and strengthening of cyber security.
- ✓ Green Transformation – consolidation of achieved effects, impact assessment and replication of successful projects.

5.1. Implementation Timeline

In order to develop a detailed timeline for the implementation of each initiative outlined in the Action Plan of the Research and Innovation Strategy, it is necessary to align the main phases and initiatives with clearly defined implementation periods. Based on the content presented in the chapters “Strategic Enablers and Key Initiatives” and “Timeline and Key Milestones”, an indicative implementation schedule is provided.

This timeline allows for the gradual yet sustainable development of a functional research and innovation ecosystem in Bosnia and Herzegovina, with clearly defined priorities and timeframes for each implementation phase. The structure of implementation dynamics is grounded in the principles of efficiency and synergy between the academic, private and public sectors.

Table 9: Indicative Implementation Timeline for Strategic Initiatives (2026–2028, by month)

Initiative / Activity	Start	End	Description / Note
Expansion of existing and establishment of new R&D and youth research grants	February 2026	December 2026	Expansion of existing grant schemes and creation of dedicated funds for young researchers.

Establishment of national and university centres of excellence	July 2026	December 2027	Establishment of thematic centres of excellence at leading universities and institutes.
Reform of doctoral studies	April 2026	June 2027	Modernisation of curricula and development of interdisciplinary and international doctoral programmes.
Collaboration with the diaspora	September 2026	December 2028	Establishment of a “Brain Gain” network, with joint research projects and mentoring schemes.
Development of TTOs, incubators and science-technology parks	May 2026	December 2028	Development and strengthening of capacities for technology transfer and support to start-ups.
Intellectual property regulations	July 2026	March 2027	Alignment of national legislation with EU standards and researcher education.
Creation of innovation funds	October 2026	September 2027	Consolidation of existing funding mechanisms and establishment of new innovation funds.
Smart specialisation strategy (S3) implementation	March 2026	June 2027	Finalisation and implementation of the national Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3).
Tax incentives and financing of innovative enterprises	July 2026	June 2027	Introduction of tax incentives for R&D investment and start-ups.
Establishment of a National Innovation Fund	October 2026	June 2027	Creation of an institutional fund to support early-stage innovation.
Incubators and accelerators	January 2027	September 2028	Development of support programmes for start-up growth through mentoring and investment networks.
Entrepreneurship education and digital skills	February 2026	December 2028	Programmes for the development of digital competences and innovative entrepreneurship.
Diaspora and private sector investment and mentorship	January 2027	December 2028	Networking of investors and mentors from the diaspora with domestic innovators.
Promotion of entrepreneurial culture	March 2026	December 2028	National campaigns and events to foster an innovation culture and vibrant start-up scene.
Establishment of the National Council for Science and Innovation	April 2026	November 2026	Establishment of a body for the coordination and strategic governance of the R&I system.
Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) system	October 2026	December 2027	Establishment of indicators and regular reporting on implementation progress.
Finalisation of S3 and launch of new strategy	June 2026	June 2027	Integration of smart specialisation into the national innovation framework.
Campaigns, mentorship and gender equality (RRI)	May 2026	December 2028	Promotion of responsible research, equal opportunities and ethical standards.

Increased participation in EU programmes (Horizon, COST, EUREKA)	April 2026	December 2028	Training and support for applications to international funding programmes.
Regional cooperation in the Western Balkans	July 2026	December 2028	Strengthening of networks and joint projects within the WB6 initiatives.
Promotion of domestic innovations in international markets	January 2027	December 2028	Participation in international fairs, missions and promotion of the innovative Bosnia and Herzegovina brand.
Forums, stakeholder portal and reports (communication with stakeholders)	May 2026	December 2028	Creation of an innovation portal, organisation of stakeholder forums and publication of annual innovation reports.
Infrastructure and digital skills (digital transformation)	March 2026	December 2027	Development of digital infrastructure and training in advanced digital tools.
Digitalisation of SMEs and legal framework	July 2026	June 2028	Voucher schemes, advisory services and alignment of the regulatory framework for e-business.
Renewable energy, circular economy and green innovation	May 2026	December 2028	Pilot projects and investments in green technologies and sustainable industry.

This timeline outlines the implementation plan for key initiatives in the field of research, development and innovation (R&I) for the period 2026–2028. The activities are grouped according to strategic pillars – from research excellence, technology transfer and innovative entrepreneurship, to digital and green transformation. The plan defines indicative start and end months for the implementation of each activity, ensuring a logical sequence of reforms, institutional strengthening and investment in the innovation ecosystem. The timeline enables coordinated implementation of measures, progress monitoring and transparent reporting on the achievement of the objectives of the national innovation and science policy.

5.2. Key Milestones for Monitoring Progress

Based on the content of the chapters related to implementation and progress indicators, a framework of key milestones has been defined for the three-year implementation period 2026–2028.

Milestones represent measurable and time-bound events or outcomes that enable continuous monitoring of progress in the implementation of strategic research and innovation priorities (Table 10).

They serve as reference points in the implementation of the Action Plan, ensuring clear tracking of achievements, timely performance assessment and the identification of any potential deviations in execution.

The following section provides a detailed overview of the defined milestones by year and month for the period 2026–2028.

Table 10: Key milestones for monitoring implementation progress (2026–2028)

Milestone	Target period	Description / Indicator
New national and university research funds established	Q4 2026	The first public calls for the funding of research projects published.

Centres of excellence established at universities	Q4 2027	Research centres formally registered and the first thematic research programmes launched.
Doctoral studies reform adopted	Q2 2027	New regulations and curricula adopted at the majority of public universities.
First joint research projects with the diaspora launched	Q2 2028	A minimum of five projects launched in cooperation with researchers from the diaspora.
Milestone	Target period	Description / Indicator
New intellectual property regulations adopted	Q1 2027	The intellectual property rights (IPR) law or regulation entered into force.
Technology Transfer Offices (TTOs) and incubators operational at universities	Q2 2027	At least three Technology Transfer Offices (TTOs) operational (UNIBL, UNSA).
Innovation fund established	Q3 2027	The first public call for innovative projects launched.
Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) finalised and adopted	Q2 2027	The document formally adopted and published in the official gazette.
Milestone	Target period	Description / Indicator
Tax incentives for startups introduced	Q2 2027	Adoption of a new tax bylaw or law.
National Innovation Fund operational	Q3 2027	First seed grants awarded.
First accelerator programme cycle launched	Q2 2028	At least 10 startups included.
Entrepreneurship education programme fully implemented	Q4 2028	Training sessions and courses conducted in all major university centres.
Milestone	Target period	Description / Indicator
National Science and Innovation Council established	Q3 2026	Decision on the establishment and appointment of members.
Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) system functional	Q4 2027	First annual implementation report drafted and published.
Milestone	Target period	Description / Indicator
Increased number of applications to EU programmes (Horizon, COST, EUREKA)	Q4 2027	At least 30% increase compared to 2025.
Joint regional projects launched in the Western Balkans	Q3 2028	A minimum of three joint projects.
Domestic innovations showcased at international fairs	Q4 2028	Participation in at least five international events.
Milestone	Target period	Description / Indicator
Digital research infrastructure operational	Q4 2027	National research network (e-infrastructure) operational.
SME digitalisation programme launched	Q1 2027	First vouchers and support measures for the SME sector published.
First circular economy and RES projects launched	Q2 2028	At least three pilot projects financed.

Milestone	Target period	Description / Indicator
National innovation portal launched	Q3 2027	Innovation portal operational and regularly updated.
Annual innovation forums organised	Q4 svake godine	At least one innovation forum held annually.
Mentoring and gender equality programmes active	Q2 2026	Active mentoring networks and programmes for women in innovation.

The milestone system is aligned with the priorities and main implementation phases of the Strategy, ranging from institutional establishment and the development of programme mechanisms, to the stage of consolidation and evaluation of results. In this way, it enables structured reporting and transparent management of the implementation process of the R&I system in Bosnia and Herzegovina.

6. Monitoring and Evaluation

- *Develop key performance indicators (KPIs)* for measuring the effectiveness of the Research and Innovation (R&I) Strategy, such as:
 - Number of start-ups established
 - Amount of funding raised by start-ups
 - Number of patents filed and technologies commercialised
 - Number of jobs created in innovative sectors
 - Number of partnerships between academia and industry (number of signed agreements)
 - R&D expenditure as a percentage of GDP, aimed at improving Bosnia and Herzegovina's position in international innovation rankings (Serbia is currently ranked 53rd according to the OECD classification)
 - Increase the number of commercially successful academic spin-off companies by 20
 - Strengthen participation in the Horizon Europe programme
 - Increase the share of graduates in science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) fields by 20%, and the share of women graduates in technical sciences by 5%
 - Establish incentives for researchers to pursue entrepreneurial careers.
- *Establish monitoring mechanisms* at both national and regional levels.

The successful implementation of the Research and Innovation (R&I) Strategy aimed at developing the entrepreneurial ecosystem in enlargement countries requires the establishment of a comprehensive monitoring and evaluation (M&E) system that will enable continuous progress tracking, outcome assessment and timely adjustment of planned measures. Such a system, aligned with the best practices of the European Union, constitutes a key mechanism for ensuring the effective realisation of strategic goals, the efficient use of resources and the increased impact of innovation activities on the socio-economic development of the region.

Monitoring and evaluation (M&E) are not merely technical processes for collecting and processing data, but strategic tools that enable evidence-based decision-making. On the one hand, continuous evaluation ensures transparency and accountability among all stakeholders; on the other, it allows policymakers and implementing bodies to respond in a timely manner to identified challenges and opportunities. The primary aim of the M&E system is to provide mechanisms for tracking the implementation of the priority measures defined in the Strategy, as well as to enable the assessment of their impact on the development of the innovation ecosystem. M&E serves as a tool for determining the extent to which strategic goals have been achieved, whether the implemented activities are yielding the expected results, and whether corrective actions are required.

6.1. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

The success of the Strategy will be assessed based on clearly defined, measurable and verifiable performance indicators. These indicators cover several key dimensions of innovation development, including the strengthening of entrepreneurial capacity, enhancement of technology transfer and the development of human capital.

Performance indicators relating to entrepreneurial capacity and innovation activity will include:

- ✓ Number of start-ups established (Business Registers of The Republic of Srpska, 2025; Judicial Commission of the Brčko District of BiH, 2025; Federal Ministry of Justice, 2025)
- ✓ Amount of funding raised by start-ups during their first year of operation
- ✓ Number of new jobs created in innovative sectors such as IT (software development and distribution), metal and electrical industries and the wood-processing industry (Government of The Republic of Srpska, 2023), with a targeted increase of 20%
- ✓ Number of commercially successful academic spin-off companies (target: 20% increase)
- ✓ Total value of approved incentives for launching innovative businesses (local, regional and national level)
- ✓ Number of research and development organisations (target: 20% increase) (The Republic of Srpska Institute of Statistics, 2024)
- ✓ Share of innovation-active enterprises (target: increase by 5 percentage points) (The Republic of Srpska Institute of Statistics, 2024).

Progress in technological development and knowledge transfer will be measured by:

- ✓ Number of patents filed and technologies commercialised (Institute for Intellectual Property, 2023)
- ✓ Number of partnerships between academia and industry (measured by signed agreements)
- ✓ Number of approved Horizon Europe and other projects supporting technological development and knowledge transfer, measured by number of projects and total value of approved funding (European Commission, 2025c)
- ✓ Percentage of the population possessing basic digital skills – targeted increase of 10 percentage points, measured by the *Economic Convergence Scoreboard for the Western Balkans* (OECD, 2025).

Research activity and the development of human resources will be monitored through the following indicators:

- ✓ R&D expenditure as a percentage of GDP, aimed at improving the country's position in international innovation rankings (The Republic of Srpska Institute of Statistics, 2024)
- ✓ Number of employees engaged in R&D activities (target: gender balance and overall increase of 10%) (The Republic of Srpska Institute of Statistics, 2024)
- ✓ Increase the share of enrolled and graduated students in science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) fields by 20%, and the share of women among graduates in technical sciences by 5% (The Republic of Srpska Institute of Statistics, 2024)
- ✓ Number of innovation research papers published in internationally recognised journals indexed in WoS (Web of Science) (Government of The Republic of Srpska, 2023), with a target increase of 20%.

A particular strength of these indicators lies in their comparability at both regional and European levels. Although target values may differ across countries, a common framework enables the comparison of trends and benchmarking of regional countries within the broader European context. Nonetheless, key performance indicators must be tailored to the specific conditions of each

country, since baseline values vary and, as such, the target values at the end of the monitoring period cannot be uniform, nor can the same percentage change be universally expected.

6.2. Data Collection, Processing and Reporting

The collection and processing of data for monitoring and evaluation of the Strategy will be based on a combination of secondary and primary sources, thereby ensuring the comprehensiveness, relevance, accuracy and comparability of information. Secondary data sources will include existing administrative and statistical databases, while primary data will be collected through targeted research where relevant information is not publicly available.

To the greatest extent, official data from national statistical institutions will be used, including the The Republic of Srpska Institute of Statistics, the Federal Institute of Statistics and the Agency for Statistics of Bosnia and Herzegovina. These institutions provide standardised and internationally comparable data on economic trends, employment, R&D expenditure, the number of enterprises by sector, as well as demographic and educational indicators. In addition, data from line ministries will be utilised, primarily the Ministry for Scientific and Technological Development, Higher Education and the Information Society (2025), and the Ministry of Economy and Entrepreneurship (2025). These sources offer insight into budget allocations, innovation support programmes, education policies and institutional capacities. For intellectual property protection — particularly the number of registered patents and protected technologies — data will be drawn from the registers of the Institute for Intellectual Property (2023), while business dynamics will be monitored using business registers, including information on the number of registered start-ups, spin-off companies and SMEs in the innovation sector. Internal data from faculties and universities will be used to monitor the number of contracts concluded between academia and industry, as well as data on the number and structure of enrolled and graduated students.

Where public data is unavailable, primary data collection will be conducted through surveys, focus groups and interviews with key stakeholders, particularly newly established enterprises, start-ups, universities and innovation support organisations. This approach will enable the collection of qualitative insights into the barriers and opportunities within the innovation ecosystem, complementing the quantitative indicators. All data will be analysed using descriptive and inferential statistical methods, as well as tools for trend analysis and data visualisation. This will ensure the validity and reliability of findings, as well as enable the tracking of progress in relation to the Strategy's defined goals and indicators.

6.3. Monitoring Mechanisms

The effective implementation of the Research and Innovation Strategy requires the establishment of clear and transparent monitoring mechanisms that will enable the systematic collection, processing and analysis of progress data. These mechanisms should ensure the timely provision of information to policymakers, research institutions and the business sector regarding results and challenges, while allowing for the adjustment of measures and activities in response to changes in the environment.

Monitoring the implementation of the Research and Innovation Strategy will be organised across multiple operational levels, with faculties and the research teams involved in the USE IPM project playing a key role. In this way, the monitoring process is brought closer to the source of knowledge and innovation creation, ensuring greater transparency, accuracy and responsiveness to emerging challenges. At the faculty level, special monitoring and evaluation teams will be established, consisting of the Vice-Dean for Research, department representatives and project activity coordinators. These teams will be responsible for monitoring the implementation of research projects, recording achieved performance indicators (e.g. number of publications, registered patents, participation in international projects, secured funding) and regularly submitting reports on the status

of key performance indicators. Members of the USE IPM project will be responsible for data collection, maintaining internal progress reports (including activity implementation timelines and obstacles encountered) and delivering these reports to the faculty monitoring team, ensuring a continuous flow of information from researchers to faculty leadership.

Additionally, participating faculties will be required to organise an annual forum for the evaluation of research activities, where research teams will present their results and discuss implementation challenges. These forums will provide opportunities for knowledge exchange among faculties from different participating countries, facilitating comparison of progress dynamics, identification of common problems and discussion of shared solutions.

At the regional level, a cooperation mechanism will be established among partner institutions from the participating countries (BiH, Serbia, North Macedonia, Albania) through the formation of a regional coordination board composed of project coordinators from each country. The board will meet once a year to conduct a comparative analysis of results, identify common challenges and propose policy alignment measures. This approach ensures that monitoring results are not confined to national boundaries, but rather serve as a foundation for mutual learning and the strengthening of the regional research and innovation community.

At the end of the Action Plan implementation period, each faculty will compile a comprehensive evaluation of the implementation of the Research and Innovation (R&I) Strategy, aimed at assessing the extent to which planned activities have been realised and determining their actual impact on the development of the entrepreneurial and innovation ecosystem. The evaluation will compare the status of success indicators at the beginning and end of the period. It will also include details on completed activities, challenges encountered during implementation and reasons for any failure to meet objectives. These reports will be used to prepare a synthesised regional report summarising the achievement of key success indicators across the participating countries.

In evaluating activity results and assessing key success indicators, the following criteria will be considered:

- ✓ Efficiency – measuring the ratio between resources used for activities (financial, human, institutional and time-related).
- ✓ Effectiveness – assessing the extent to which target KPI values were achieved.
- ✓ Impact – evaluating the long-term effects of the Strategy on the entrepreneurial ecosystem, including those that may only emerge after the implementation period.
- ✓ Sustainability – assessing whether the results and effects of the Strategy are likely to be sustained, particularly with regard to the stability of funding and the durability of links between academia, the private sector and public institutions.

The evaluation methodology will be of a mixed nature and will include the following analyses:

- ✓ Quantitative analysis – quantifying the number and percentage of fulfilled individual KPIs.
- ✓ Qualitative analysis – conducting focus groups or interviews with key actors involved in the Strategy's implementation (researchers, business representatives, start-ups, etc.) to gain insight into opportunities and obstacles within the innovation ecosystem.
- ✓ Comparative analysis – comparing results and achievements across the enlargement countries to identify good practices and shared challenges.

This approach provides a comprehensive overview of KPI achievement and enables the identification of both shared and country-specific challenges. The implementation of the Research and Innovation Strategy lays the foundation for the development of a sustainable innovation ecosystem in the enlargement countries, the effects of which should be further strengthened and expanded in the future.

7. Risk Management

Within the framework of implementing the Research and Innovation Strategy, crisis management is regarded as an essential component of the resilience of the entire ecosystem. Particular emphasis is placed on anticipatory management, which is based on the early identification and monitoring of risks, as well as the systematic supervision of key indicators that may signal potential disruptions. Through continuous monitoring of the financial stability of start-ups, regulatory changes and international trends, it is possible to develop preventive measures that reduce the likelihood of a crisis occurring in the first place. In this regard, scenario planning also plays an important role, including the development of simulations that allow for the identification of various potential outcomes and the preparation of appropriate responses. The anticipatory approach also entails the development of flexible institutional capacities, diversification of funding sources and the establishment of stable partnerships with the academic and business sectors, thereby making the ecosystem less vulnerable to external shocks. As noted by Williams et al. (2017), linking research on crisis management and organisational resilience demonstrates that a proactive approach enables faster adaptation and mitigation of the negative effects of uncertainty.

Nevertheless, it is not possible to avoid crises entirely, which is why reactive management also plays a vital role, ensuring a rapid and coordinated response once a crisis has occurred. In this context, clearly defined roles and the establishment of operational crisis teams are of key importance, as they enable swift, coordinated and effective action. Crisis communication is also of particular importance and must be transparent and consistent towards all stakeholders, as the preservation of trust and the legitimacy of the Strategy depend on it. Reactive management also includes a business continuity plan, ensuring the continuation of critical research and innovation activities even under emergency circumstances, as well as post-crisis evaluation. In this way, organisations not only address the consequences but also learn from each crisis and use those experiences as a basis for strengthening future plans (Bundy et al., 2017).

Combined, anticipatory and reactive management constitute a coherent framework that allows for the forecasting and mitigation of crises where possible, and for efficient and decisive responses when they are unavoidable. This dual approach not only reduces the negative effects of potential disruptions but also fosters a culture of resilience within the research and innovation ecosystem, thereby enhancing its long-term stability, competitiveness and sustainability. At the same time, combining anticipatory and reactive approaches builds trust among all stakeholders, as it demonstrates that the system possesses both a long-term development vision and the capacity to confront unforeseen challenges.

8. Conclusion and Recommendations

Bosnia and Herzegovina holds genuine potential to accelerate its transition towards a knowledge-based economy, provided that higher education institutions — in particular, the University of Banja Luka and its Centre for Project Management and Entrepreneurship (CPME) — maintain a pivotal role in knowledge transfer, engagement with the private sector and the development of open innovation within the framework of the Quintuple Helix model. The proposed R&I Strategy and Action Plan are fully aligned with the priorities of the European Commission (Horizon Europe, S3, ERA and the Green Deal), drawing on a combination of empirical methods including desk research, Delphi studies, focus groups and quantitative surveys. The three interconnected pillars — research excellence, technology transfer and exploitation, and innovative entrepreneurship — form the foundation for building systemic capacity and sustainable cooperation between academia and industry.

Key challenges remain low innovation intensity, weak policy coordination and insufficient institutional support. For this reason, the European Commission recommends the urgent adoption of a national R&I strategic framework with a clearly defined action plan and performance indicators. In

this context, the establishment of a joint body for the coordination of research and innovation policy is advised, tasked with implementing a monitoring and evaluation system and ensuring regular progress reporting. A second priority is the adoption of a national R&I strategy with an S3 component and the setting of quantified targets (e.g. increasing R&D expenditure to at least 1% of GDP by 2030 and doubling the number of innovative start-ups within five years).

The role of universities should be further strengthened through the development of a network of technology transfer offices, the establishment of innovation laboratories and the introduction of internal grant schemes. It is necessary to launch an innovation fund with a dedicated early-stage support line (Proof of Concept, seed capital) and to develop support programmes for academic spin-offs and SMEs. Horizontal priorities should include digital and green transformation, through the creation of digital innovation hubs and green pilot projects aligned with the EU agenda. Furthermore, international cooperation must be enhanced, including participation in Horizon Europe and COST programmes, and activation of the diaspora as partners and mentors. The establishment of permanent platforms for dialogue with industry and civil society, and the systematic communication of results through annual reports and a dedicated R&I portal, will contribute to transparency and the strengthening of an innovation-oriented culture.

The proposed measures derive from the three pillars of the strategy and European recommendations. Their strength lies in their interconnectivity, clarity of objectives and measurable outcomes. The rapid establishment of a coordination body, the adoption of an R&I strategy with S3 logic and the creation of an early-stage development fund represent the first steps (“quick wins”) that can enhance institutional credibility and generate momentum for a broader reform of Bosnia and Herzegovina’s research and innovation system.

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ANNEX

Reviews of the D2.4 Action Plans for R&I Strategy Implementation

Review 1	
Reviewer Name:	Panayiotis Kontakos, PhD, Deputy Head of School of Business and Management, Assistant Professor in International Business, UCLan, Cyprus, SAB member
Date of review:	20/12/2025
Reviewer opinion: (150 words)	The deliverable “Action Plans for R&I Strategy Implementation” is fully aligned with the objectives outlined in Grant Agreement No. 101120390. No further revisions are required by the author or other partners of the USE IPM consortium. General opinion: Accepted; Comments: None.
Review 2	
Reviewer Name:	Marija Radosavljevic, PhD, PC, FEUN
Date of review:	18/12/2025
Reviewer opinion: (150 words)	The deliverable named “Action Plans for R&I Strategy Implementation” is in line with the Grant Agreement for project No. 101120390. This document will serve as a strong anchor through the USE IPM project. Therefore, the quality of this deliverable is acceptable to be further processed to the European Union through the SyGMa platform. There is no need for further improvements of the deliverable by the writer and other partners of the USE IPM consortium. General opinion: Accepted; Comments: None.